

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

Be.CULTOUR: “Beyond CULTural TOURism: human-centred innovations for sustainable and circular cultural tourism”

HORIZON 2020

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Report of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon best innovative solutions for sustainable cultural tourism

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Dissemination Level

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Abstract

Under the frame of Be.CULTOUR, Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM – ISFSC (hereinafter abbreviated as ICHEC) launched a call for passionate innovators eager at shaping the future of cultural tourism in Be.CULTOUR's six partner European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova. The call was open from 02 March until 19 May 2022 at Be.CULTOUR website.

Applicants submitted their concept notes via EU Survey platform and in total, 35 applications were received. Overall, six local juries, one in each Pilot Heritage Site (PHS), were set up to evaluate the concept notes. Applicants were invited to pitch their innovative solutions before a local jury.

Following each local jury deliberation, 19 innovative circular cultural tourism solutions were selected from Be.CULTOUR 6 Pilot Heritage Sites to travel to Brussels and participate in Be.CULTOUR hakathon at ICHEC. Be.CULTOUR hackathon took place from 07 to 09 September 2022. During the three intensive days, 76 innovators co-working in 19 teams moved collaboratively from idea generation to first solution prototyping. 19 videos were shot by ICHEC communications department & made available at Be.CULTOUR website for a public vote online. In two hours, 2083 votes had been cast. In tandem, 5 parallel juries took place at ICHEC during which each team had the opportunity to pitch its project to high level expert jurors.

Be.CULTOUR hackathon award ceremony took place in person at ICHEC and was also livestreamed on ICHEC's YouTube channel. The main award was the 4-month acceleration period offered by ICHEC to the 19 teams.

Moreover, additional awards were sought and offered to the most voted on-line solution and to the favourite innovative circular cultural tourism solution of each of the five juries.

Partners involved in the document

Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Check if involved
1 Coordinator	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Institute of Heritage Science	CNR	
1.1	University of Naples Federico II – DiARC (Linked Third Party)	UNINA	
2	European Regions Research and Innovation Network	ERRIN	
3	ICLEI Europe – Local governments for Sustainability	ICLEI	
4	Iniziativa Cube S.r.l.	INI	
5	Uppsala University	UU	
6	Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM - ISFSC	ICHEC	X
7	Open University of the Netherlands	OUNL	
8	APT Basilicata	APT-BAS	
9	Diputación Provincial de Teruel	PGT	
10	Larnaca and Famagusta Districts Development Agency	ANETEL	
11	Laona Foundation	LAONA	
12	Västra Götaland region	VGR	
13	Stalna Konferencija Gradova I Opstina	SCTM	
14	Agentia Pentru Dezvoltare Regionala Nord-Est	NERDA	
15	Verde e Moldova	VEM	

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1. Description of the Project

Be.CULTOUR stands for “Beyond CULTural TOURism: heritage innovation networks as drivers of Europeanisation towards a human-centred and circular tourism economy”. It expresses the goal to move beyond tourism through a longer-term *human-centred* development perspective, enhancing cultural heritage and landscape values.

Cultural tourism entails opportunities but also risks. Tourism as a whole can be a highly volatile economic sector. If not managed properly, cultural tourism can also easily turn into a “value extractive” industry, generating negative environmental, social and cultural impacts on local communities and ecosystems. This project will **develop specific strategies to promote an understanding** of cultural tourism, which moves away from a “stop-and-go” consumer-oriented approach towards one that puts humans and circular economy models at its centre, paying attention to nature, communities and cultural diversity. “Place”, intended as the *genius loci*, the ancient spirit of the site expressing its “intrinsic value” and “people” as co-creators of its uniqueness, culture, art, tradition, folklore, productivity, spirituality, as well as its “time space routine”, are the focus of Be.CULTOUR, which aims at realizing a longer-term development project for the pilot areas involved.

The overarching goal of Be.CULTOUR is to **co-create and test sustainable human-centred innovations for circular cultural tourism through collaborative innovation networks/methodologies and improved investments strategies**. Targeting deprived remote, peripheral or deindustrialized areas and cultural landscapes as well as over-exploited areas, local **Heritage innovation networks** will co-develop a long-term heritage-led development project in the areas involved enhancing **inclusive economic growth, communities’ wellbeing and resilience, nature regeneration** as well as **effective cooperation** at cross-border, regional and local level.

Wide and diversified partnerships of stakeholders from **18 EU and non-EU regions** of Northern-Central and Southern Europe, the Balkans, the Eastern neighbourhood and the Mediterranean will be the driving force of the project. A **community of 300 innovators** (which includes regional authorities and municipalities, clusters and associations, museums and tourist boards, entrepreneurs, chambers of commerce, citizens, researchers, practitioners as well as project partners) in **6 pilot regions** will **co-create innovative place-based solutions for human-centred development through sustainable and circular cultural tourism**.

Collaborative “Heritage innovation networks” will be established in **6 European deprived remote, peripheral and deindustrialised areas and cultural landscapes** identified as “pilot innovation ecosystems”: committed to the project’s objectives, they have defined clear cultural tourism-

related challenges requiring innovation that will serve as the basis for the collaboration with the **16 additional “mirror innovation ecosystems”**. Mutual learning and up-scaling of business solutions will be the objectives of the collaboration between pilot and mirror ecosystems, building the sustainability of the project's results beyond its lifetime.

By adopting a human-centred quadruple/quintuple helix approach to co-design, **Be.CULTOUR will result in 6 community-led Action Plans, 18 innovative human-centred solutions and 6 close-to-market prototypes** of new cultural tourism integrated services and products: these will directly contribute to **inclusive economic growth, communities’ wellbeing and resilience, and nature regeneration** in pilot and mirror regions, **stimulating effective cooperation** at a cross-border, regional and local level. The core partners of the Consortium will progressively build Be.CULTOUR sustainability by broadening the interregional collaboration while anchoring it to relevant EU initiatives in the academic, business and institutional realms.

1.1 Be.CULTOUR specific objectives

The scopes of the Be.CULTOUR project will be achieved through a set of specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-constrained (SMART) specific objectives:

Objective 1 – To assess the impacts and market potential of sustainable and circular cultural tourism at national, regional and local level through multidimensional quantitative and qualitative indicators, innovative statistical methods and advanced smart data management systems;

Objective 2 – To build a Community of Practice of 6 pilot regional ecosystems and a Community of Interest with 16 “mirror ecosystems” in EU and non-EU countries actively engaged in knowledge-sharing and exploitation of Be.CULTOUR’s approach, methodology, tools, and innovative solutions for sustainable and circular cultural tourism;

Objective 3 – To co-develop 6 Action Plans for sustainable and circular cultural tourism by establishing collaborative “Heritage innovation networks” in 6 pilot regions in Northern-Central and Southern Europe, the Balkans, the Eastern neighbourhood and the Mediterranean;

Objective 4 – To co-develop, prototype and test human-centred and place-specific product, process and service innovations for sustainable and circular cultural tourism in pilot heritage sites;

Objective 5 – To provide policy recommendations for more effective use of European Structural Investment Funds (ESIFs) and other EU funds to support cultural tourism innovation ecosystems in pilot and mirror regions, and develop a proposal of evolution of ESIFs through synergies with other public funds;

Objective 6 – To contribute to deepen cultural Europeanisation through information and educational activities focused on the European history, identity and culture expressed in tangible and intangible cultural heritage and cultural landscapes, developing European Cultural Routes and European Heritage Labels in pilot heritage sites.

All partners have wide experience in developing and testing the Be.CULTOUR proposed approach, methodology and tools, ensuring the effective and time-constrained achievement of all the above-mentioned specific goals.

2. Introduction

Based on its extensive experience in co-creation and business innovation in the field of circular economy and cultural heritage, Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM – ISFSC (hereinafter abbreviated as ICHEC) launched a call for passionate innovators eager at shaping the future of cultural tourism in Be.CULTOUR's six partner European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova. The call was open from 02 March until 19 May 2022 at Be.CULTOUR website.

Initially, the idea, as stated in the Grant Agreement, was to select one innovative circular cultural tourism solution from each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site (PHS). Following several bilateral and collective meetings with Be.CULTOUR six PHS, it was decided to select three innovative circular cultural tourism solutions from each PHS with the exception of four innovative circular cultural tourism solutions from the Pilot Heritage Site Route of Stephan the Great and Saint seen that the route represents a cross-border area which connects north-east Romania and Moldova. Therefore, two solutions were selected from each country. The reasons behind this choice were to: give each PHS the possibility of exploring more innovative solutions and award the most appropriate one(s) for the sustainable development of its territory; provide training opportunity for more people from the territory during the hackathon and acceleration period; and to create a community of Be.CULTOUR innovators which could better contribute to the local action plans. Starting from the challenges linked to the targeted deprived, remote or over-exploited areas, the selected participants were invited to develop circular cultural tourism services and/or products that focus on creating attractive destinations taking into account post COVID-19 pandemic scenarios.

Applicants submitted their concept notes via EU Survey platform and in total, 35 applications were received. Overall, six local juries, one in each Pilot Heritage Site (PHS), were set up to evaluate the submitted concept notes. Applicants were invited to pitch their innovative solutions before a local jury in each PHS. Following each local jury deliberation, 19 innovative circular cultural tourism solutions were selected from Be.CULTOUR 6 Pilot Heritage Sites to travel to Brussels and participate in Be.CULTOUR hackathon at ICHEC. The objective was to give the 19 teams the possibility of co-developing, testing and prototyping their solutions.

ICHEC designed and implemented Be.CULTOUR Hackathon for innovative circular cultural tourism solutions from 07 to 09 September 2022. During the three intensive days, 76 innovators co-working in 19 teams moved collaboratively from idea generation to first solution prototyping. In

addition to the 19 teams, registered partners and stakeholders from Be.CULTOUR pilot and mirror regions participated in some sessions of Be.CULTOUR hackathon.

19 videos were shot by ICHEC communications department & made available at Be.CULTOUR website¹ for a public vote online. In two hours, 2083 votes had been cast. In tandem, 5 parallel juries took place at ICHEC during which each team had the opportunity to pitch its project before a high-level expert jurors².

Be.CULTOUR hackathon award ceremony took place in person at ICHEC and was also livestreamed on ICHEC's YouTube channel³. The main award was the 4-month acceleration period offered by ICHEC to the 19 teams. Moreover, additional awards were sought and offered to the most voted on-line solution and to the favourite innovative circular cultural tourism solution of each of the five juries. In total, 6 additional awards were offered.

2.1 Document structure

The document is structured as follows:

Section 1 describes the project and its objectives

Section 2 provides an introduction

Section 3 presents Be.CULTOUR call for proposals;

Section 4 introduces applications selection process;

Section 5 outlines Be.CULTOUR Hackathon implementation.

¹ <https://becultour.eu/hackathon>

² <https://becultour.eu/meet-jury>

³ <https://lnkd.in/ehDDGc4A>

3 Be.CULTOUR call for proposals

3.1 Be.CULTOUR call preparation

Deliverable D3.4 “Report on Challenge-driven innovation in Be.CULTOUR regions⁴” outlined PHS main challenges, while D3.1 “Protocol/Methodology for human-centred innovation in sustainable and circular cultural tourism” mapped their aspired innovation areas. However, during Be.CULTOUR participatory Local Workshops (LWS), the stakeholders mapped additional innovation areas and the Pilot Heritage Sites challenge statement were amended as well. Since Be.CULTOUR call was intended to tackle the concrete territorial challenges and trigger innovation areas of interest, and in order to reflect what the Community of Practice (CoP) mapped during Be.CULTOUR LWS, ICHEC carried out six bilateral meetings with each of the six PHS⁵.

During the bilateral calls, the eligibility criteria was thoroughly discussed in relation to context-based needs. In addition, the geographical scope; language; hackathon and acceleration period timelines; what is expected from each team; Hackathon and acceleration period schedules were exhaustively addressed as well. Moreover, PHS were asked whether they were ready to embrace, support and implement the winning solutions beyond the lifetime of Be.CULTOUR. Wooclap was used to raise the questions and trigger the discussion (Figure 1) during each bilateral call.

Moreover, the award modality was discussed, and existing procurement procedures were explored.

Finally, PHS were advised to design a tailored dissemination strategy in order to reach out to as many innovators as possible in their territory as well as at the national level.

⁴ D3.4 “Report on Challenge-driven innovation in Be.CULTOUR regions. Available at: <http://becultour.eu/sites/default/files/2022-02/D3.4%20%E2%80%93%20Report%20on%20Challenge-driven%20innovation%20in%20Be.CULTOUR%20regions.pdf>

⁵ 26/11/2021 08:30-10:00 ANETEL, LAONA & ICHEC; 26/11/2021 10:30-12:00 NERDA and VEM & ICHEC; 29/11/2021 10:30-12:00 VGR & ICHEC; 01/12/2021 10:30-12:00 APT-BAS & ICHEC; 02/12/2021 08:30-11:00 PGT & ICHEC; 03/12/2021 11:00-12:30 SCTM & ICHEC.

The screenshot shows the 'wooclap' interface for a 'Hackathon timeline'. At the top, there's a blue header with 'wooclap' on the left and 'My events Ruba Saleh EN' on the right. Below the header, the title 'Hackathon timeline' is followed by a 'Participate at' link: 'app.wooclap.com/PTLPPN'. There are also 'Share' and 'Settings' buttons. Below this, there are tabs for 'VOTES', 'MESSAGES', and 'PARTICIPANT PACE'. The main content area lists seven questions, each with a 'DISPLAY' button and an 'EDIT' button. The questions are: 1. Is the timeline reasonable for you?, 2. Do you prefer an open call or an invitation?, 3. What is your geographic scope?, 4. How many languages would you like to see embedded in the solution?, 5. Group gender equality, 6. Are you open to mixing proposals?, 7. Are you committed to embrace, support and implement the winning solutions? There is also a 'How to participate?' section at the top with a 'DISPLAY' button. A search icon is visible on the right side of the interface.

Figure 1 - Be.CULTOUR hackathon timeline

On 21st January 2022, ICHEC sent a draft call for proposals, an application form and an informed consent form including a declaration of commitment to each PHS to revise by 4 February 2022. PHS were requested to provide rich background information about their region and Pilot Heritage Site, describe thoroughly their PHS challenges and the aspired innovation area(s). In tandem, ICHEC organised bilateral call with each PHS in order to deep dive into the proposed text and needed tweaks. Between 31st and 2 February, bilateral meetings with each PHS took place to answer questions.

On 9 February 2022, a collective meeting with the six PHS took place and was specifically dedicated to tackle questions related to: ethics, copyright, GDPR privacy issue and related consent form, award-giving and procurement procedures, local juries and the evaluation criteria. In total 7 calls were prepared and launched. A comprehensive call, terms and conditions for the six PHS and an ad-hoc call for each PHS tackling its geographic scope, specific challenge and innovation areas. ICHEC Data Protection Officer (DPO) revised and approved “Be.CULTOUR call for proposals, terms and conditions” (annex 1), incl. the call’s related “Informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data” and privacy policy, and the “application form” on EU Survey (annex 2).

3.2 Be.CULTOUR call for proposals content

Following the feedback and approval from Be.CULTOUR six PHS, Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals was structured into sixteen sections.

Section 1 set the scene by explaining that under the frame of the Horizon 2020 funded project 'Beyond Cultural Tourism (Be.CULTOUR)', ICHEC launched a call for passionate innovators to shape the future of cultural tourism in Be.CULTOUR's six European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova. Moreover, it specified that 19 applications will be selected to participate in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022. Furthermore, it was highlighted that selected applicants will be given the opportunity to access Be.CULTOUR Accelerator, a training programme of 4 months aimed at developing the innovative solutions to a close-to-market stage. Finally, the section provided background information about H2020 project Be.CULTOUR, consortium partners and the project objectives.

Section 2 elucidates the rules of the call. It, therefore, clarifies how the team should be composed and what needs to be submitted; what is meant by an innovative solution, its level of maturity, the innovation areas and the specific area for the development of the innovative solution. Section 2 is described in Deliverable D3.2 – Protocol/Methodology for human-centred innovation in sustainable and circular cultural tourism (Part 2).

Section 3 informed the applicants about the possibility of participating in the LWS and the importance of linking the innovative solutions with Be.CULTOUR local Action Plans for circular cultural tourism co-designed by the local community in each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site. Each PHS call included the date, place and either a registration link or email of the contact person and invited applicants to sign up.

Section 4 explains the selection process. It specifies that the applying teams will be invited to pitch their innovative solution locally. It also describes what a hackathon is and that selected teams by their PHS local jury will be invited to a 3-day hackathon in Brussels. It also highlights that applicants are expected to commit to travel to Brussels and participate actively in the 3-day Be.CULTOUR Hackathon. Such commitment was presented as the medium for accessing later on Be.CULTOUR acceleration programme and the opportunity to develop and test their innovative solutions. This section clarifies also what the applicants are expected to do during every day of the hackathon, the timeline and why to participate in the hackathon.

Section 5 presents the award which is a 4-month acceleration period offered by ICHEC. It also explains what an acceleration period is, what they are expected to learn during this period, and it provides a structured program and timeline.

Section 6 explicates application modality: where and how to apply and application deadline.

Section 7 delineates the evaluation process and selection of applicants. It describes the evaluation criteria and the mark attributed to each criterion.

Section 8 points out that after the acceleration period, Be.CULTOUR project will give the innovators the possibility to develop their Minimum Viable Product and test it in real context by applying for monetary support according to the principles of transparency, competition and best value for money in compliance with the rules of each country.

Section 9 discloses the acceptance of terms and conditions.

Section 10 defines how the project intends to protect the intellectual property.

Section 11 clarifies how confidentiality will be ensured by the organisers.

Section 12 spells out how the advertising rules for finalists and winners. It specifies that the the EU emblem and Be.CULTOUR logo should be used together with a specific text clearly highlighted in the call

Section 13 walks the applicants through the Privacy and Data Protection Policy. It also provides a link to the full privacy policy⁶ in a pdf format.

Section 14 explains what Be.CULTOUR Consortium may use, for its communication and publicising activities, information relating to the action, documents and any other material (such as pictures or audio-visual material) that it receives from the applicants (including in electronic form).

Section 15 clarifies the rules of modifications and cancellations.

Section 16 reveals the fact that the Terms and Conditions are governed by Belgian law and the applicants and the Organizers, expressly waiving any other jurisdiction, are subject to the Court of Brussels, Belgium, for any dispute arising between the parties. The language before the court will be French.

The call includes also annexes. Annex 1 provides definitions for each innovation area and the main concepts of H2020 project Be.CULTOUR framework. While annex 2 provides the Informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data for each of the four teammates.

⁶ <https://becultour.eu/hackathon/privacypolicy>

4. Call selection process

4.1 Call dissemination

The call was disseminated through Be.CULTOUR website⁷ and social media. Initially, interested parties were invited to apply between 02 March at 07:00 (CET) and 02 May 2022 at 23:00 (CET) in the six PHS. Be.CULTOUR website provided access to:

- the open call- terms and conditions;
- the 6 different open calls;
- the privacy policy;
- the informed consent form;
- a sample application form; and
- the link to EU survey application form

Pilot Heritage Sites also disseminated the call through social media, local workshops and info sessions. Direct reach out to local innovators who might be interested in applying or have innovative ideas of interest to the PHS was privileged.

For example, in Serbia the call was announced in Serbian in the news⁸, it was published on the website of Be.CULTOUR partner Stalna Konferencija Gradova I Opstina (SCTM)⁹, on Facebook¹⁰ and Twitter¹¹. SCTM also shared it through its newsletters, relevant e-groups (working bodies and teams) and promoted it through ad-hoc events. Finally, one-to-one calls were also performed.

ICHEC provided a weekly update to the six PHS on the number of submitted applications. In reference to the open call.

On 28 April 2022, a collective meeting took place in order to assess the state of the art and agree on the strategy for attracting more applications. A Wooclap poll summarizes the discussed topics during the meeting (Figures 2-6). Bilateral calls were also scheduled to discuss the applications, the local jury composition and evaluation criteria. All partners agreed to extend the call till 12 May 2022 in order to provide additional time to groups who expressed interest to register during the LWs. Finally, the call was extended for one more week until 19 May 2022 upon a request by two PHS.

⁷ <https://becultour.eu/becultour-call-innovative-solutions>

⁸ <http://skgo.org/vesti/detaljno/2868/poziv-za-podnosenje-predloga-za-najbolja-inovativna-resenja-za-cirkularni-kulturni-turizam-u-opstinama-bac-sremski-karlovcima-i-irigu>

⁹ <http://skgo.org/konkursi/detaljno/310/poziv-za-podnosenje-predloga-u-okviru-projekta-becultour-inovativna-resenja-za-cirkularni-kulturni-turizam-u-bacu-sremskim-karlovcima-i-irigu>

¹⁰ <https://www.facebook.com/SKGO.SCTM/posts/4938480732906131>

¹¹ https://twitter.com/skgo_sctm/status/1499404990560964614

Figure 2 - Be.CULTOUR call poll Q1

Figure 3 - Be.CULTOUR call poll Q2

Figure 4 - Be.CULTOUR call poll Q3

Figure 5 - Be.CULTOUR call poll Q4

Figure 6 - Be.CULTOUR call poll Q5

On 19 May 2022 at 23:00 the call was closed. In total, 35 applications were received as follows:

Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy (3 applications)

- Cammino Lucano
- Fly On Tour Immersivo
- Triple L tourism Leave, Learn

The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain (5 applications)

- Aridscape the wide as heritage
- Eco glamping
- La chica cabeza de bosque
- OLIETE GREEN CIVILIZATION
- UMAMI

Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus (5 applications)

- Kalosorisetse
- Larnaca Renaissance Festival
- Monument app
- Needle festivals
- Sensory Bee Nature Trail

Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden (4 applications)

- Create, Design & Engage
- Forsviks Choice
- Prova-Bo long-term rentals
- Rydalskonceptet

Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia (8 applications)

- BAČ BY TOUCH
- BISK-MULTICULTURAL FAIRY TALE
- Cultural overload - Irig road
- Film location hunting
- FRUŠKING 8x4x4
- Heritage Summer Festival
- Irig eco edition of tradition
- Tourism XR Bike Tour

The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area (10 applications)

Moldova (3 applications)

- E-cool tour
- Stephan route update
- Steven's path - S Path

Romania (7 applications)

- A virtual journey of heritage
- Digital Nomads Platform DNP
- Know thy history know theyself
- REVE Heritage
- Stephen the Great's Wine Route
- The Bison Land's Heritage
- VR route

4.2 Local juries set up and deliberation

Each Pilot Heritage Site (PHS) invited between 8-13 people to act as jury members. The six PHS were advised to take gender equality into consideration and to invite knowledgeable professionals about the needs of their PHS while representing a multiplicity of stakeholders including public & private sectors, civil society organisations and minorities.

The six PHS were also advised to host the jury meeting for a maximum duration of two hours. Where the first hour is dedicated to pitching. Each team representative was requested to pitch for a maximum of 10-minutes covering the topics addressed in the application form. A pitching timeline was also provided to the six PHS. Moreover, the six PHS provided each applicant (team) with Be.CULTOUR Logo together with the EC logo with Be.CULTOUR grant agreement number.

Before the pitching session, each jury member received:

- a consent form adapted to the national law and requirements of each PHS.
- jury member registration form
- open call (annex 3)
- evaluation criteria (annex 4)
- submitted concept notes¹².

Overall, six local juries, one in each Pilot Heritage Site (PHS), were set up to evaluate the concept notes¹³. Following the local juries' deliberations, 19 innovative circular cultural tourism solutions were selected from Be.CULTOUR 6 PHS to travel to Brussels and participate in Be.CULTOUR hackathon between 07-09 September 2022 in order to move from idea generation to first solution prototyping.

¹² Personal data was not shared with the jury. The email of each group representative was shared following a written approval by the latter with the concerned local coordinator of each PHS in order to enable her/him to invite the team to pitch its solution before the local jury.

¹³ The local juries took place on the following dates: The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain (Tuesday 24 May 2022), Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus (Friday 27 May 2022), Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden (Monday 30 May 2022), Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia (Thursday 26 May 2022), the Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area (Tuesday 24 May 2022).

4.3 Call selected innovations

The 19 selected innovative circular cultural tourism solutions were the following:

Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy (3 applications)

Innovative circular cultural tourism solution	Abstract
Cammino Lucano	<p>This solution promotes a "slow" travel method that allows people to get to know Basilicata from unexpected points of view that cannot be perceived by hit-and-run tourism that transform the journey into an unforgettable experience, towards the realization of our deep identity.</p> <p>It is projected towards the creation of a cultural path capable of providing a tourist experience connected to the intimate and deep stretches of Lucania through the Municipalities of: Melfi, Rapolla, Barile, Ginestra, Ripacandida, Rionero in Vulture, the lakes of Monticchio, Atella and San Fele.</p> <p>Later it will be projected towards the realization of a real physical journey among the memories of a world that no longer exists, immersed in the beauty of the nature of Lucanian creation, to the rediscovery of the Marian representations dedicated to Santa Maria di Costantinopoli in Ginestra and Barile, the sanctuaries of Atella and Melfi where the Marian representations with a dark complexion are kept, without forgetting the most important sanctuary of Lucania dedicated to San Michele in Monticchio lakes.</p> <p>This solution investigates the celestial reasons for the arrangement of the churches of Santa Maria di Costantinopoli, of the ancient places of worship dedicated to San Michele and the Black Madonna, which in a mirror-like manner underlie the constellation of the Pleiades. Almost an artistic idea; which seeks what is "designed" in Heaven for something plastically made on Earth by our ancestors, is the core of the research: Heaven and Earth ideally connected to suggest a unique Marian Way. The work carried out in the implementation of the Way will serve to consolidate the services offered by the various reception structures already present in the area, and to give impetus to the birth of new activities, to develop that fullness of the response, to the growing demand represented by new tourist flows, again to be fully implemented on the territory.</p>
Triple L tourism Leave, Learn	<p>The proposal consists in organizing classes in Venosa of temporary residences for students (Italians and foreigners, in particular for the latter, opening the possibility that they can carry out the entire Erasmus period in the location chosen) in collaboration with the University of Basilicata.</p> <p>To the students of the various fields (in particular cultural heritage operators, techniques for building and land management, agricultural technologies, forestry and environmental sciences, landscape-environment and urban greenery, engineering for the environment and the territory, anthropological and geographical sciences for cultural heritage and the enhancement of territories, European history and civilization, architecture...) will be asked to invent, experiment, create urban, environmental and cultural projects to enhance and promote above all the Via Appia and Herculea and forms of tourism linked to slow movement (aimed at walkers and bikers). The idea is to create a new community in Venosa and then in the villages, through living in a place temporarily but constantly.</p>
Fly On Tour Immersivo	<p>FlyOn is passion for flying, for authentic knowledge of places, for the exploration of inaccessible areas, for accessible tourism. The use of visors and FPV (First Person View) technology allows you to watch and experience unfamiliar or morphologically impossible locations or simply enjoy a panoramic view with professionally piloted drones. Our Mission is to break down architectural barriers, giving people with motor disabilities the opportunity to visit inaccessible places.</p>

Table 1 - Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy applications

The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain (3 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	Circular tourism	Abstract
Eco glamping		<p>Teruel has an incredible landscape that is fairly unknown. This solution wants to involve the local inhabitants to show our patrimony in a sustainable way. We have local artisanal products. Local guides, local people and local food which will provide a unique experience.</p> <p>We want to spread our word and our nature all around Spain. We want to use our clean sky to spend incredible nights under the stars. We will be in contact with nature in small sustainable glamping spaces.</p>
Aridscape the wide as heritage		<p>Our proposal is based on the necessity of people to work, to live and to enjoy nature and heritage. Our aim is to restore architectural heritage not monuments but vernacular architecture and create small offices to bring people to work, offering at the same time a comfortable place to live in the same building. We think that if we get to do this we could work in different projects about architectural heritage and landscape which could create positive impact, increasing the possibilities of new sustainable tourism.</p> <p>While people are working in their offices, they could even collaborate in projects out of the computer, learning about traditional materials and constructive techniques through the restoration of stone and sand walls, giving them some notions about that through practical courses.</p> <p>This experience not only help to create an innovative and circular tourism, but it also helps to set up new population in small towns. In this proposal we want to take advantage of our wonderful landscape, a landscape of sand, mood, and drought tolerant plants. This type of landscape offers us a really wide vision which is difficult to find in the rest of Europe, with almost no roads, no towns, no lights and a really clear sky at night. But this arid landscape offers us also all those materials to restore our more valuable heritage: our traditional architecture.</p>
La chica cabeza de bosque		<p>Our project "La Chica Cabeza de Bosque" –which in Spanish means "The Forest[1]Headed Girl"– is composed by four people that came from diverse locations and share a common objective: to highlight the positive elements of our homeland such as the cultural, social and ethnographic components. Our main objective, and the reason why we created "La Chica Cabeza de Bosque", is to enrich the cultural heritage and biodiversity of Teruel by making use of resources like water, land, vegetation and locations. We aim to make ethnobotany and horticultural therapy accessible to people so that it gives value, growth and development not only to our area but also to the people interested in our work. We want to bring our knowledge about plants, flowers and trees closer to the people by emphasizing their benefits in human health from a holistic approach to mental health.</p>

Table 2 - The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain applications

Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus (3 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	Abstract
Sensory Bee Nature Trail	<p>Troodos Network in cooperation with the Deputy Ministry of Tourism and Larnaca Tourism Board, have developed the Honey Routes, a network of 9 villages with the highest density of Beehives and Beekeepers due to the amazing landscape and flora of the area. A lot of experiential workshops are organized in the area, 3 Festivals, are taking place every year, the first one in May is aligned with the World Bee Day and is devoted to the importance of Bees as pollinators for the existence of our planet, the second one in June is devoted to the products of the Hive and Beekeeping and the 3rd one in September is devoted to Bees and children so that environmental culture and awareness is created from the very young stage.</p> <p>Each festival attracts 4,000 visitors and bring to the area a substantial income which is extremely beneficial for the area and the Beekeepers bearing in mind that these villages were completely unknown before this initiative and the lack of public transport and distance from cities is an obstacle for rural tourism. Beekeeping is not simply a way of survival in the area for the young keepers who have decided to practice it as a profession, but also a part of their cultural heritage, as it has been practiced for centuries and honey is used in ways and recipes that can only be found in the area. Continuous efforts are taking place for the upgrading of the Honey Routes, by training and capacity building of the local communities, encouragement of the women to create micro business based on their skills and their natural resources, protecting the environment, but also upgrading the area with innovative tools, which will create unique experiences for the visitors. The aim of the Sensory Bee Nature Trail is to create a range of experiences with the use of technology to feel the life and sounds of bees which have been proven very beneficial for calming the brain and learn how the community of the Hive lives and create their precious products.</p>
Monument app	<p>Year-round festivals with the mission to discover and explore Cypriot identity through cultural, entrepreneurial and sports activities. While embracing the rural landscape, the festivals will disrupt the status quo as social opportunity spaces for participants, to explore and elaborate on Cypriot identity: how it appears in daily life, sound, taste, and aesthetic through sensorial experiences and emerging relationships. The seasonal thematic events will aim at building a tight-knit community from the bottom up, by connecting artists, entrepreneurs, traditional businesses, the elderly and athletes. Through a holistic experience that will include artisan workshops, nature exploration activities, camping, art exhibitions, music festivals and many more. The festivals will provide an environment for questioning, observing, networking, and experimenting and its driving force will be a creative community that will bring people together to explore and embrace their roots, traditions and history. Territorial innovation in this case can be achieved by bringing the society together, mixing the boundaries of arts, culture, sports and business fields for social interaction and ideation.</p> <p>Needle Festivals will therefore facilitate a learning experience that will be based on connecting diverse people with nature through fun and play activities to celebrate learning and knowledge transfer in a safe environment. The mission is to expand the serendipity field of Pervolia area by creating social opportunistic spaces. Our business model is based on connections and networking, and we vision to facilitate a community.</p>
Kalosorisete	<p>A web-based application, that people visiting Cyprus can book online experiences, based on Cypriot culture, and the Rural Area of Larnaca. The system will have a back end and a front-end side. People hosting the experience will be able to manage their bookings and incomes. On the front side visitors will see all the information of the individual experience and book and pay on the spot.</p>

	<p>kalosorisete wishes to give opportunities and extent the working horizons of people in rural areas. Craftsmen and craftswomen, lovers of customs and traditions of our island will be hosted on this platform.</p> <p>There might be other platforms that offer experience to tourists. Our aim is to offer authentic Cypriot experience to visitors, to curious people that wish to explore Cyprus beyond sun and sea. We wish to improve the standard of living for rural people in terms of the environment they will live in. The whole process will be based on a mobile application that both visitor and host will be able to manage their bookings and available products. The application will be available for android and IOS users. All suppliers / hosts by default must be locals. They are those who know the customs and traditions and wish to promote this to travellers. To the best extent possible, the locals could employ locals and further we will use the saying "leading by example". People in the rural area of Larnaca will see the benefits these people have by participating on this platform and they might wish to join. Employing locals is at the heart of what we do. We believe in the power of the circle economy and recycling. We strongly promote the re-use of products and materials or if this is not possible, we promote the policy of recycling</p>
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Table 3 - Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus applications

Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden (3 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	circular tourism	Abstract
Forsviks Chalice		<p>Forsviks Cultural Heritage, Arts and Innovation Centre (CHAICE)</p> <p>The idea is to establish a community, cultural, (hand)crafts and innovation centre in the located historical buildings of an old foundry which currently "just" host events, theatre and arts exhibitions. We see potential for a future rural equal and included meeting place to add a cafe, seminars, education lessons, leisure time facilities for children, teenager and young grownups and "tankesmedja" (think tank) workshops, as in a base for new ideas which shall perpetuate the Be.CULTOUR project.</p>
Prova-Bo rentals	long-term	<p>Our proposal "Prova-Bo" (translated to "Try-Living") is a long-term rental platform with the goal of increasing the number of permanent residents living in rural areas by lowering the thresholds to move there both financially, mentally and socially. Local communities in rural areas struggle with depopulation due to urbanization and an aging population. As they become more dependent on attracting tourists to survive, the identity of these places change. With our project we hope to strengthen the local communities' action of power to shape their own future. At the same time, we see that many people are willing to move from the cities to rural areas. However, big parts of Sweden remain anonymous and since buying is the norm in the countryside, the threshold for moving can therefore be big.</p> <p>With Prova-Bo we want to show how we can meet current needs and challenges based on what already exists and by threatening the built environment as a scarce resource. What we have seen is that in many places residential buildings can be used in a more efficient way that benefits both the house owners and the local society.</p> <p>Through Prova-Bo new rental apartments can be created within the existing housing stock. It could be a regional or even global platform to which local communities through a local association can connect and present themselves. When visiting the platform online people looking for a place to settle down can read more about the connected local communities with available rentals. On site all private rental options are gathered and administered by the local association in close relation to the house owners. Part of rent goes to the local association for common development projects.</p>

	The platform supports an increased number of year-round residents and thereby strengthens important services throughout the year such as grocery stores, schools, public transport etc. and by that, their dependency on tourism is reduced.
Create, Design & Engage	<p>There are many similarities between Rydal, Sweden and Saltaire, UK, starting with both Mills at the heart of each community were built in 1853. The two locations have a tradition of industry contributing to cultural heritage of the respective locations. This industrial cultural heritage infrastructure provides an interesting canvas for creative and cultural exploration for artists, that provides a unique stimulus for the creation of contemporary community narratives and generate interesting experiences for residents and visitors.</p> <p>Saltaire Inspired has been identified as utilising innovative strategies that involve the local community through human and community centred approaches to valorise local heritage. This project application is to establish deeper and sustainable engagement programmes to build on these relationships and share practice and projects between Sweden and Saltaire. We would like to develop a conceptual framework of the process of establishing an international partnership and share an understanding of this process for replicability in our respective regions as well as beyond. At the heart of this programme there is a commitment to exploring the process of creating sustainable circular cultural tourism experiences - 1. physical gatherings between artists and the local community leading to co-created programme design, development and implementation; 2. professional development opportunities identified by participants, and 3. publications, digital tools and exhibitions of work. We believe that student internship opportunities should be built into the programme to ensure the nurturing of young people, succession planning and ensuring learnings are not lost.</p> <p>The main challenge for us is thinking about a) firstly, what is important for us to know about ourselves and each other, b) which tools should we adopt to communicate effectively that gives us both the autonomy as well as connectivity, and c) developing an effective methodology to gather the learnings so that the innovations can be replicated.</p>

Table 4 - Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden applications

Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia (3 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	Abstract
Frušking 8x4x4	<p>Frušking is a new word in the Serbian language, which we invented for the need of the project within the Be.CULTOUR competition. The first part of our neologism comes from the adjective fruški – which means belonging to Fruška Gora. Additionally, the term represents flirting with English because it is associated with English words ending in –ing, such as: walking, biking, hiking... When you add everything together you get walking, biking and hiking across Fruška Gora. Besides addition, there is also multiplication: 8x4x4. These are the dimensions of the mystery box which the tourist will get when they visit us. When the box is opened out there are 32 stories inside about 32 places, 32 wines of Fruška Gora and 32 historic figures. All this in such a small box? Yes, and there is also room for one more thing and a few more possibilities: a map facing the east (because the word orientation originated from the word orient and also Tolkien wrote that dwarves made maps in this way); a possibility to travel by luck and one more possibility – to determine the route after a thorough research and by one’s own choice. And what if the choice is happiness? Then you are on the right track. Frušking is a remedy for frustration and a stress reliever. When a human is deep down in the forest they connect with the primordial</p>

	and realize that they are not and cannot be a guest in nature. Following the map facing the east the tourist reconnects with oneself.
Cultural overload - Irig road	<p>The digital map of Irig will provide potential and on-site tourists with information about natural and cultural heritage, stories, photos, videos about the sights, with elements to increase their engagement. This will be a personal tour guide available 24/7. It involves creation of new tourism product – selection of attractions which would be the part of digital map of area and education of suppliers to be the part of tourism product.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Selected suppliers will be educated to offer standardized product. -Attractions will be described. -Each visit will be personal and memorable with customized welcome and exit messages. -The platform will have option to send Push notifications to all visitors in destination to alert visitors to a special point of interests, event or promotion. -Digital map will offer location-based interactive games that visitors can play, ensuring a new opportunity for further bringing of groups for team buildings, to attract new segments during workdays. -Every visitor will leave the area with a shareable video moment of their visit incorporating destination branding. This is automatically generated from the pictures and videos that the visitor takes during their time in destination. -The platform will allow tourism policy makers to see the location of the visitors in area at any given moment. This will help control crowding and see what points are the most popular and how long they keep visitors on the spot. Besides that, this will be an easy opportunity to get feedback from the visitors. This will be an important trigger for the tourism policy makers for future steps – which points are the key attractions. -This application will have the opportunity for tourists for social responsibility – information for fundraising for cultural heritage. -There is a possibility of generating more revenue by booking tickets and accommodation offered via platform.
Bač By Touch	<p>After years of experience of working and volunteering in cultural institution, heritage sites, travel and youth organisations, we have thought of this project as a proper implementation of contemporary experience for tourists who seek modern solutions in tourism. During the COVID pandemics, all of us have noticed the increased need of remote and digital solutions in tourism and cultural preservation. In the aspect of digital technologies, in the recent years, especially in the smartphone industry, "touch" technology has been widely used and especially viable in the younger population.</p> <p>We have come up with an idea to make an interactive touch-screen display, which would contain various programs and solutions in the form of one digital environment, that would contain virtual and sensorial experience, promotion of cultural heritage, local enterprises, households, rural tourism, and nature preservation. In regard to virtual and sensorial experience, our plan has been to make virtual environment where it would be possible to experience many aspects of medieval life at the Bac Fortress, which also contains 3D dynamic audio, characters that will be responsive to a set of questions about the Bac area, in the form of multiple-choice dialogue. The environment would also contain the entire medieval fortress, natural wildlife, possible random events at a chosen date, and a virtual councillor tour guide for adults and youth.</p> <p>Moreover, our team would create a website that would offer promotion of all the aforementioned goals, and in addition to that, it would contain the whole experience in an Android application that would be available for downloading at several app stores.</p> <p>The expected outcome of this project is to raise interest in tourism and cultural heritage in the younger population, connect the enterprises, to make the information</p>

	easily accessible and internationally available in several languages, to save time needed for tourists to get to know the place, etc.
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Table 5 - Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia applications

The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area (4 applications)

Romania (2 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	circular tourism	Abstract
Digital Platform DNP	Nomads	<p>The Digital Nomads platform - Hero's Journeys in Northeast Romania is based on the common template of stories that involve a hero who goes on an adventure, is victorious in a decisive crisis, and comes home changed or transformed. In the highly volatile today's work environment, we aim to become a one-stop-shop solution for highly skilled digital workers (individuals and their families), to choose our region as a work - live - explore destination for up to 6 months.</p> <p>The platform will explore each individual's unique needs and skill set through a hero lens that will match their profile with a recommended journey as a digital recipe (from local accommodation to tourism experiences to freelance local jobs). Each journey will be connected to history bits from the Stephanian route. When choosing to work & live from the Northeast region and their hero journey, the digital nomads access an authentic experience co-created by local actors and carefully curated in our Digital Nomad platform.</p> <p>The project is unique due to the gamifying the user's experience, facilitating early immersion in the region by taking over roles (personas) from the local heritage, while offering a complete work-in/live-in package. The solution can be easily scaled and adapted to other regions, adapting the characters to local history.</p>
The Bison Heritage	Land's	<p>The main aim of the solution is to offer a unique experience for the tourists of the Bison Land, trying to combine and to value in a holistic way the certain natural, cultural and spiritual features of the area. In Bison Land there are situated two objectives of the ROUTE OF STEPHAN THE GREAT AND SAINT (Neamt Fortress and Neamt Monastery) and other attractions mentioned in the BeCULTOUR project: Vanatori Neamt Nature Park and Agapia, Varatec, Secu and Sihastria monasteries. The monastic population is around 1,100 monks and nuns, the natural heritage is represented by a huge, forested area, where the large carnivores of Carpathians and the iconic species of European bison are present.</p> <p>Nowadays the tourists are interested especially by the monasteries, neglecting the natural heritage and traditional aspects of the area. This can be transformed into a huge opportunity which will allow to enhance the local identity, the wellbeing, the local business, the biodiversity protection and to reduce pollution. In order to realize this unique experience our proposal takes into consideration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -new trails or adapting the actual trails that will assure a connected spiritual and natural travel experience through a proper interpretation and small infrastructures as" forest bathing", rest benches, panels etc. In addition, guided tour, including wild fauna observation, especially for the European bison, will be provided by the local guides. -a treasure hunt application, based on the local Route's objectives and the above trails. The application will be bilingual, with QR codes and AR elements, assuring an educational environment and visitors' retargeting. -culinary events will assure a sensorial heritage experience, emphasizing the natural settings or the human tangible and intangible heritage (folk craftsmen, local products,

	music and dance). The events will be positioned in close relation with the Route's objectives and trails.
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Table 6 - The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania applications

Moldova (2 applications)

Innovative cultural solution	circular tourism	Abstract
E-cool tour		<p>ECoolTour is an innovative easy-to-use platform that generates special touristic routes based on the preferences of the user.</p> <p>This route will contain not only a visit to some attractions, but will also include restaurants, with the cuisine chosen by the user and if needed a place to stay overnight. The user will be able to pay everything inside the platform, but also give an important feedback and rating to each location visited. The smart rating will help improve our database and algorithm, which will make every next route better for the next customers.</p> <p>It will have also an ability of registration for different entertainment providers, restaurant and hotel owners and different types of small and medium sized businesses, which will help diversify each touristic site. The ability to add specific places to a site will also make it really easy to solve one of the actual problem with the given route of Stephen the Great (Ștefan cel Mare), which lacks some of the key sites that Stephen the Great has visited throughout His time, such as: the site of the Lipnic Battle; Lăpușna Royal Court; Pârcălăbia Cioburciu; etc. Our platform will correct and complete these and other shortcomings in the route of Stephen the Great.</p> <p>A great opportunity opened by a digital solution, makes it easy to integrate different other cultural routes, such as: Medieval trade routes; Ancient and medieval fortifications; Ethno-gastronomic routes. And will be easy to give the information exactly how and when we want it to be pursued, so it makes sense in different circumstances.</p> <p>All in all, this app is calculated, in such a way, that it is a good organizational tool for everyone involved in the touristic industry, not only for the business owners that will find new clients, but also for regular people who just want an interesting weekend trip, in a new interesting location.</p>
Stephan route update		<p>The digital platform is based on the website dedicated to the first cross-border route in the region under the name "Voivode Stephen the Great and Saint". The web platform presents a unique opportunity for tourists who want to follow the tourist route and be the creators of their own route. Being up to date with the principles of sustainable development and information technologies, we aim to come up with a unique solution for history and culture lovers by applying digital solutions and accessing the route in an online format. The digital solution we propose is to connect all the tourist attractions within the route through information panels with direct access to the digital platform of the route through a QR code, this stage being already implemented in the Republic of Moldova. Each tourist during his trip will be digitally connected to all the locations of the tourist route. By traveling on the route "Voivode Stephen the Great and Saint" in the Republic of Moldova or in the North-East region of Romania, tourists will live an authentic and remarkable experience.</p>

Table 7 - The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, Moldova applications

Each team, composed by 4 teammates, was requested to confirm availability to participate in the hackathon and acceleration period. One team from Larnaca PHS (Monument app) declined and was replaced by Needle Festivals. In total 76 innovators from the 6 PHS confirmed their participation. At the end of June 2022, the 19 confirmed teams received a dossier including the list of innovative solutions and participants and the hackathon guideline (annex 5).

5. Be.CULTOUR hackathon implementation

5.1 Be.CULTOUR hackathon methodology

A hackathon is a design sprint event that brings together professionals from different walks of life. It spans from multiple hours to a few days during which multidisciplinary teams brainstorm and solve a challenge, create a product prototype or conduct a case study. The hackathon format was selected because it provides a unique opportunity for teams to collaborate intensively on the development of their ideas into desirable, feasible and viable projects and it is known to be the shortest route to innovation.

Be.CULTOUR Hackathon aimed at developing circular cultural tourism services and/or products that tackles the challenges of Be.CULTOUR PHS deprived, remote or over-exploited areas and contributes to the sustainable and human development of the territory. It embraced a highly participatory approach which allowed to move from idea generation to first solution prototyping. It combined plenary sessions where the methodology and tools were presented with group work implementing the design thinking process with the help of mentors. During each session/day, a time for reflection was planned and coaching was provided by ICHEC Brussels Management school coaches. By the end of each day, each team was expected to complete a number of deliverables on its own Miro. Be.CULTOUR Hackathon was structured around three main pillars :

- the 4 pillars of a successful solution;
- the 5 stages of the Design Sprint 3.0 methodology; and
- the Societal Impact Canvas

The 4 pillars of a successful solution

During the 3- day hackathon, the 19 participating teams were introduced and coached on how to move from idea generation to first solution prototyping and end up with a minimal solution that is desirable, feasible, viable and impactful (Figure 7).

When addressing the value proposition and its key features, the coaching focused on challenging mental ceilings and on clarifying that a desirable solution responds to concrete needs of target users/customers/segments which are not yet addressed by a competitor.

Under human, physical and digital capital, the coaching challenged the feasibility of the solution by exploring the key activities at the heart of the value proposition and the needed capabilities and partnerships to bring the solution to life.

For the business model, the coaching concentrated on economic viability. The teams were mentored to co-develop economically sound revenue streams and financial model. Finally, in terms of impact the coaching motivated the teams to activate positive social and environmental impacts by embracing circularity and the human-centred approach.

Figure 7 - The 4 pillars of a successful solution

The 5 stages Design Sprint 3.0 methodology

Be.CULTOUR hackathon adopted the 5 stages of the Design Sprint 3.0 methodology aimed at developing human-centred and circular solutions. During the first two stages, “UNDERSTAND” and “DEFINE” the teams:

- investigated the actual and pressing stakes from societal impact perspectives i.e. circular and people dimensions;
- encompassed a human-centred design approach by collecting key needs, pains and expected gains thanks to interactions with target customers’ and users’ segments.

Stage 1, “UNDERSTAND” had the objective of gaining a full understanding of: the causes and consequences related to the challenge that the team wants to address; the stakeholders ecosystem; the value chain actual needs, and pains and expected gains of target customers / users. While stage 2, “DEFINE”, targeted creating consensus around: key challenging stakes; and customer segments’ needs to be addressed by the solution.

Stage 3, “IDEATE”, enabled teammates to strengthen their solution by tapping into inspiring examples of circular and people-centred solutions provided by the organizers. This stage aimed at defining an augmented solution nourished by inspiring examples and combining teammates’ insights.

Finally, stages 4 “PROTOTYPE” and 5 “TEST”, allowed teams to test the relevance of their solution vs actual needs. Therefore, keeping a human-centred design approach. The purpose of stages 4, “PROTOTYPE”, was to design a minimal testable solution ready to be tested from desirability, feasibility, viability, and impact perspectives. While stage 5 “TEST”, had the ambition of testing minimal testable solutions & updating them based on lessons learnt.

The Societal Impact Canvas

The Societal Impact Canvas (Figure 8) is an evolution of the classical Business Model and Lean Canvases. It embeds the societal impact dimension from different perspectives:

- “**Raison d’être**” aka purpose positioning humans and sustainability at the heart of the solution;
- “**Value Propositions**” that cover not only the functional dimension but also focus on environmental (circular) and social (people) dimensions;
- Societal impacts** where environmental and social positive impacts are demonstrated;
- Reallocation of potential profits and surpluses** as lever of further positive impacts;
- Governance** as a way to embrace key stakeholders’ perspectives and to keep human centrality in the development of the solution.

The use of the societal impact canvas helped the participants to visualise the 4 pillars of a successful solution: desirability, feasibility, viability, and impact.

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Company : _____ Date : _____ Version : _____

Figure 8 - The societal impact canvas

5.2 Be.CULTOUR hackathon day by day implementation

Day1: Understanding my Pilot Heritage Site and circular cultural tourism

During the first day of the hackathon, the morning sessions were dedicated to mapping the context, the value chain and empathising with stakeholders. While the afternoon sessions were dedicated to testing the innovative solutions and empathizing with different segments from the team’s stakeholder map (see full programme in annex 5).

Day 1 was dedicated to stages 1 “UNDERSTAND” and 2 “DEFINE”. Under stage 1 “UNDERSTAND”, each team completed the following deliverables: drafted a list of assumptions, mapped stakes and selected the ones to tackle, defined the user/client segments and co-designed the empathy map of needs (jobs to be done, pain points & gains). Moreover, under the framework of stage 2 “DEFINE”, the deliverable focused on the most important needs to be tackle. In order to get acquainted with the concepts and translate the results of the group reflection, the following tools were used: Cause & effect tree, Stakeholder map, Value chain map, Target users & customers map, Interview guide, Empathy map, Customer/user stories & the Team canvas.

Figure 9 - Welcome remarks by ICHEC's rector Prof. Brigitte Chanoine

Figure 10 - Practical remarks by dr. Ruba Saleh

Figure 11 - Introduction to Be.CULTOUR hackathon methodology by Philippe Drouillon

Figure 12 - Energizer

Figure 13 - Preparing for the “Empathize” phase

Figure 14 - Retrospective: Learning as a team

Day 2 focused on stage 3 “IDEATE” in the morning and introduced stages 4 “PROTOTYPE” & 5 “TEST” in the afternoon. Under stage 3 “IDEATE”, each team described its solution and components and based on the needs, checked whether the solution was fit. The 19 teams were invited to virtually “get out of the building” by getting in touch with beneficiaries and clients through phone calls and videoconferencing. Under stage 4 “PROTOTYPE” the value propositions were defined and Pretotype v1 was built. Finally, under stage 5 “TEST”, both the value propositions and Pretotype v1 were tested. In order to get acquainted with the concepts and translate the results of the group reflection, the following tools were used: Societal Impact Canvas (Figure 8), Minimum Viable Solution Board, Value Proposition Board and the Riskiest Assumption Tests (RAT) Board.

At the end of Day 2 a visit and networking event took place at LaVallée¹⁴. A creative hub which boosts artistic and artisanal production in the heart of Molenbeek. LaVallée hosts cultural entrepreneurs, artists, coworking spaces and exhibition and workshop spaces. It aims at helping emerging creatives and offering workshops and activities to disadvantaged communities. Be.CULTOUR innovators had the possibility to visit the spaces and discover the mission and vision of this positive impact creative hub. Moreover, Be.CULTOUR Mirror regions and partners joined for a networking dinner and it was a great opportunity for the innovators to exchange and learn about other European experiences.

¹⁴ <https://lavallee.brussels/?lang=en>

Figure 15 - Introduction to stage 3 "IDEATE"

Figure 16 - Stage 3 "IDEATE" solution design: diverging phase

Figure 17 - Stage 3 "IDEATE" solution design: converging phase

Figure 18 - Stage 4 "PROTOTYPE"

Figure 19 - Stage 4 "PROTOTYPE": First Minimal Testable Solution (MTS)

Figure 20 - Stage 5 "TEST": Assessment of the most critical assumptions (RAT) via phone interviews

Figure 21 - Stage 5 "TEST": Cross-team Feedback session - Dry test

Figure 22 - Visit to LaVallée

Figure 23 - Exchanging with a resident of LaVallée

Figure 24 - Networking at LaVallée

Day 3 was devoted to stages 4 “PROTOTYPE” & 5 “TEST”. Under stage 4 “PROTOTYPE” the feasibility of the solution was accomplished by the 19 teams during the morning session. In parallel, 19 one-minute videos were shot by ICHEC communications department & made available by ERRIN¹⁵ at Be.CULTOUR website for a public vote online. Each team was provided with the video specifications in the hackathon guidelines (annex 5) and reminded to respect it during the hackathon coaches. Teams were instructed to prepare a script of 150 words maximum which address the following three questions:

- What is your innovative solution about? What's your secret sauce that makes the difference?
- What positive impacts / transformations does it bring to your Pilot Heritage Site?
- What is your motto?

Moreover, the first 1st viability equation and impact assessment were carried out under stage 4. The deliverables of this stage focused on: the viability of the solution by quantifying revenue streams and cost perspective in running mode and the feasibility of the solution. In order to get acquainted with the concepts and translate the results of the group reflection, the following tools were used: the Monetization scheme and the skills, capabilities, assets map.

Under stage 5 “TEST”, the pretotype v1 was updated and pretotype 2 was tested. The deliverables of stage 5 focused on: visualising the Business model and impact and test the last prototype. In order to do so, the following tools were used: Business Model Visualization frame and the Impact wheel. Finally, pitches were prepared based on a standard presentation provided by ICHEC.

¹⁵ <https://becultour.eu/hackathon>

Figure 25 - Introduction to the programme of Day 3

Figure 26 - Monetisation scheme presentation

Figure 27 - Video shooting at ICHEC

Figure 28 - Refreshing coffee break before the award ceremony

5.3 Be.CULTOUR hackathon award

At the end of Day 3, the 19 teams pitched their innovative circular cultural tourism solutions before five parallel high-level juries¹⁶. Each jury just evaluated 3 or 4 solutions under the lens of two innovation areas as follows (Table 1):

Jury	Solutions
Jury 1: Sensorial heritage experience & Rural co-living experience	Pitch 1: Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live Pitch 2: Sensory Bee Nature Trail Pitch 3: Create, Design & Engage Pitch 4: FRUŠKING 8x4x4
Jury 2: Contemporary meaning of heritage, Spiritual Travel experience	Pitch 1: Camino Lucano in Vulture Pitch 2: Cultural overload - Irig road Pitch 3: Stephan's route site update Pitch 4: The Bison Land's Heritage
Jury 3: Post cultural tourism & Industrial Heritage Experience	Pitch 1: Fly On Tour Immersivo Pitch 2: Forsviks Choice Pitch 3: Prova-Bo long-term rentals Pitch 4: BAČ BY TOUCH
Jury 4: Nature as heritage experience & Proximity Travel	Pitch 1: Eco glamping under the stars Pitch 2: La chica cabeza de bosque Pitch 3: Needle Festivals
Jury 5: Transformative travel & Remote working experience	Pitch 1: AridScape The wide as heritage Pitch 2: Kalosorisete Pitch 3: Digital Nomads Platform Pitch 4: ECoolTour

Table 8 - Jury composition

In tandem with the pitching session a back to back voting was open on Be.CULTOUR website for two hours. At the end of deliberations, the on-line voting was stopped. The award ceremony took place in plenary and was also live streamed on ICHEC YouTube channel¹⁷.

During the award ceremony, the main award aka four months acceleration training for the 19 teams offered by ICHEC was announced. ICHEC's rector Prof. Brigitte Chanoine thanked each team and handed over a certificate of attendance to each teammate. Following this exciting moment, colleagues from ERRIN reported that 2083 votes have been cast. Finally, additional awards (Table 2) were sought by ICHEC and revealed as follows:

¹⁶ <https://becultour.eu/meet-jury>

¹⁷ <https://lnkd.in/ehDDGc4A>

Jury	Winning solution	PHS	Award
Jury 1: Sensorial heritage experience & Rural co-living experience	Sensory Bee Nature Trail	Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus.	Keynote speech at the European Alliance group Culture thematic seminar, European Committee of the Regions offered by jury member Kieran MCCARTHY, Member of SEDEC, European Committee of the Regions
Jury 2: Contemporary meaning of heritage, Spiritual Travel experience	Stephen's route site update	The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area	Access to the network of the winners of ILUCIDARE Special Prizes offered by jury member Prof. Koenraad Van Balen and H2020 project ilucidare consortium.
Jury 3: Post cultural tourism & Industrial Heritage Experience	Forsviks CHAICE	Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden	Attendance at Hostelworld Conference 2023! Including Flight/Hostel Stay/Local Experience offered by Hostelworld Group.
Jury 4: Nature as heritage experience & Proximity Travel	Eco glamping under the stars	The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain	Keynote speech at the Working group on cultural heritage and tourism offered by ERRIN.
Jury 5: Transformative travel & Remote working experience	Kalosorisete	Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus	Keynote speech at Breakfast at Sustainability's (B@S) offered by ICLEI Europe.
Popular online vote	BAČ BY TOUCH (538 votes)	Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia	coaching session on Business Modelling and fundraising and an invitation to a competition on art-tech and culture-tech in Switzerland offered by jury member Vincent Favrat, Founder and manager at scale up

Table 9 - Additional awards

Figure 29 - Sensorial heritage experience & Rural co-living experience

Figure 30 - July 4: Nature as heritage experience & Proximity Travel

Figure 31 - Award ceremony kicks-off

Figure 32 - Visualisation of the 19 videos

Figure 33 - Certificates hand over to the three teams from Serbia

Figure 34 - Certificates hand over to the four teams from Romania and Moldova

Figure 35 - Winning solution Stephen's route site update

Figure 36 - Winning solution BAČ BY TOUCH

Figure 37 - Winning solution Forsviks CHAICE

Figure 38 - Winning solution Kalosorisete

Figure 39 - Winning solution Sensory Bee Nature Trail

Figure 40 - Winning solution Eco glamping under the stars

Acronyms

[CE]	[Circular Economy]
[CoP]	[Community of Practice]
[Col]	[Community of Interest]
[DPO]	[Data Protection Officer]
[EC]	[European Commission]
[EU]	[European Union]
[HCD]	[Human-Centred Design]
[HIN]	[Heritage Innovation Networks]
[HUL]	[Historic Urban Landscape]
[IA]	[Innovation Area]
[IS]	[Innovative Solutions]
[LWS]	[Local Workshops]
[GA]	[Grant Agreement]
[PHS]	[Pilot Heritage Site]
[SDGs]	[Sustainable Development Goals]
[WP]	[Work Packages]

Annex 1 – Be.CULTOUR CALL FOR PROPOSALS, TERMS AND CONDITIONS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020 – Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals

Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions Hackathon and acceleration opportunity

Reference: Terms and conditions

Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites:

- Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy
- The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain
- Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus
- Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden
- Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
- The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

Innovation areas:

- Rural Co-living
- Sensorial Heritage Experience
- Contemporary Meanings of Heritage
- Spiritual Travel experience
- Nature As Heritage
- Industrial Heritage Experience
- Transformative travel
- Remote Working Destination
- Proximity Travel
- Post-cultural tourism

Deadline for submission of application:

May 19th 2022 at 18:00 (CET)

Call for proposals
2 March 2022

1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020 – Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals Terms and conditions

SUMMARY

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the frame of the Horizon 2020 funded project 'Beyond Cultural Tourism (Be.CULTOUR)', Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM – ISFSC (hereinafter abbreviated as ICHEC) is opening a call for passionate innovators to shaping the future of cultural tourism in six European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova.

19 applications will be selected to participate in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon which will take place in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

Selected applicants will be given the opportunity to access the Be.CULTOUR Accelerator, a training programme of 4 months in which they will have the possibility to develop their innovative solutions to a close-to-market stage.

Starting from the challenges linked to the targeted deprived, remote or over-exploited areas, the selected participants will develop circular cultural tourism services and/or products that will focus on creating attractive destinations taking into account post COVID-19 pandemic scenarios.

1.1 BACKGROUND

ABOUT Horizon 2020 Be.CULTOUR PROJECT

Be.CULTOUR stands for 'Beyond CULTURAL TOURism: heritage innovation networks as drivers of Europeanisation towards a human-centred and circular tourism economy'. The overarching goal of Be.CULTOUR is to foster sustainable regional development through circular cultural tourism. The project will develop human-centred innovations inspired by cultural heritage, to support the transition of the tourism sector towards a circular economy.

Title of the project	Beyond Cultural Tourism
EU programme	Horizon 2020 (Innovation Action)
Duration	36 months, starting from 1 st February 2021
Coordinator	CNR-IRISS Italian National Research Centre - Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)-IRISS (IT) • Iniziativa Cube (IT) • Uppsala University (SE) • European Regions Research & Innovation Network (ERRIN) (BE) • ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability (DE) • ICHEC – Business management school (BE) • OUNL – Open University of the Netherlands (NL) • APT-BAS - Association for territorial promotion in Basilicata (IT) • PGT - Provincial Government of Teruel (ES) • ANETEL -Larnaca and Famagusta District Development Agency (CY) • LACNA Foundation for the Conservation and Regeneration of the Cypriot Countryside (CY) • VGR - Cultural Development Administration Region Västra Götaland (SE) • SCTM - Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities National Association of Local Authorities in Serbia (RS) • NERDA - North-East Romania Regional Development Agency (RO) • VEM - NGO Verde e Moldova (MD)

Cultural tourism entails opportunities but also risks. If not managed properly, it can easily generate negative environmental, social and cultural impacts on local communities and ecosystems. Moreover, the level of development of cultural tourism between certain regions and sites, including those between the neighbouring countries in Europe, remains still unbalanced. Deprived remote, peripheral or deindustrialised areas lag behind, whereas high demand areas are over-exploited in an unsustainable manner.

Moreover, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has brought global, urban, and regional development and cultural tourism to a standstill, hitting all territories without distinctions and seriously jeopardising thousands of European cultural and tourism professionals' livelihoods. Despite the challenges, the tourism and culture sectors today face a unique opportunity to develop innovations towards more circular and resilient future. They are bound to reinvent and diversify their offer, attract new audiences in different ways, and develop new skills to support this radical transition. Capitalising on digitalisation, supporting circular tourism and promoting less exploited areas are now key to build a stronger, more sustainable and resilient tourism sector.

In February 2021, the Horizon 2020 funded project “Beyond Cultural Tourism – Be.CULTOUR” was launched with precisely this ambition. Selected with the maximum score amongst 86 proposals. Be.CULTOUR has 4 million Euros and 3 years to help regions develop human-centred and circular models for their cultural tourism sector. Led by the CNR IRISS, Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development in Italy, the consortium comprises 15 partners including research institutes, local and regional authorities, as well as European umbrella organisations.

Six EU and non-EU territories have accepted the challenge: the regions of Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Västra Götaland (Sweden), Vojvodina (Serbia) as well as the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova will be equipped with tools, knowledge and contacts to accelerate the development of innovative solutions in different thematic areas (Rural Co-living, Sensorial Heritage Experience, Contemporary Meanings of Heritage, Spiritual Travel experience, Nature As Heritage, Industrial Heritage Experience, Transformative travel, Remote Working Destination, Proximity Travel, Post-cultural tourism) and test them with a wide and diversified partnership of stakeholders in each site.

By adopting a human-centred quadruple/quintuple helix approach to co-design, Be.CULTOUR will result in 6 community-led Action Plans, 19 human-centred innovative solutions and at least 6 close-to-market prototypes of new cultural tourism integrated services and products: these will directly contribute to inclusive economic growth, communities' wellbeing and resilience, and nature regeneration in pilot sites, stimulating effective cooperation at cross-border, regional and local level.

19 teams will be selected and awarded to join the Be.CULTOUR Community of innovators and will have access to a training programme 100% funded by Horizon 2020 and dedicated to passionate innovators in charge of shaping the cultural tourism sector of the future!

More information on the project is available at: <https://www.becultour.eu/>

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THIS CALL FOR PROPOSALS

The Objective of this Call for Proposals is to select and award the best 19 innovative solutions for circular cultural tourism development in remote and less-known destinations in Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites¹, focusing on their specific challenges and areas of innovation².

Therefore, this call aims at creating innovative circular cultural tourism services and/or products in the following Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites:

- Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy
- The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain
- Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus
- Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden
- Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
- The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

The innovative solution should address the following three main concepts of Horizon 2020 Be.CULTOUR framework and definition of circular cultural tourism³, namely:

Circular economy in tourism

Human-centred design & development

Cultural tourism as driver of Europeanisation

While encompassing the following innovation areas:

- Rural Co-living
- Sensorial Heritage Experience
- Contemporary Meanings of Heritage
- Spiritual Travel experience
- Nature As Heritage
- Industrial Heritage Experience
- Transformative travel
- Remote Working Destination
- Proximity Travel
- Post-cultural tourism

Moreover, digitalisation and smart data management features will be considered a plus. Please find in ANNEX 1 the definition provided for each innovation area considered in this Call together with the three main concepts of Horizon 2020 Be.CULTOUR framework and definition of circular cultural tourism.

¹ Pilot heritage sites are the specific territorial areas in which the Be.CULTOUR project aims to test and validate innovative approaches to regional development through circular cultural tourism. See also: Be.CULTOUR Glossary <https://www.becultour.eu/glossary/>

² For each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site and its related challenges, please check the specific open call on H2020 Be.CULTOUR website: <https://becultour.eu/Hackathon>

³ Circular cultural tourism in BeCULTOUR project defines a sustainable and regenerative cultural tourism model that aims to foster sustainable and equitable regional development implementing a “human-centred” circular economy model through the enhancement of abandoned, underused and less-known cultural and natural resources, enhancement of human capital and human rights, reduction of tourism pressure on over-exploited territories, reduction of wastes and natural resources consumption (energy, water, soil, biodiversity), increase of clean energy and green transport means, recycling and reuse of materials and products, and enhancement of locally based food and craft productions – finally empowering local communities, enhancing ecosystems, enhancing local identity, wellbeing, health and cultural diversity, and enhancing local entrepreneurial innovation ecosystems through cultural tourism. See also: Be.CULTOUR Glossary <https://www.becultour.eu/glossary/>

2. RULES FOR THIS CALL FOR PROPOSALS

The following guidelines set out the rules for the submission, selection and implementation of the solutions in the above mentioned Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites.

2.1 ORGANISER

The organiser is as mentioned in this call ICHEC.

2.2 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

There are two sets of eligibility criteria, relating to the:

- composition of the team (see §2.2.1)
- minimum innovative solution(s) requirements (see §2.2.2)

2.2.1 COMPOSITION OF THE TEAM

-This Call for Proposals is open to individuals, companies, associations, foundations, institutions, and other entities (either individually or in association), which have a direct or indirect interest in intervening and/or contributing to the development of circular cultural tourism in one of Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites.

-Whether individual or in association, each application should be submitted by a team made of 4 people⁴.

-At least one team member should be able to speak and write in English.

-If the entire group is composed by individuals, preferably at least one team member should be a representative of a legal entity (i.e. have a VAT number or equivalent status).

-Participants should be preferably resident (in case of individuals) or legally registered (in case of organisations) in the following countries: Italy, Spain, Cyprus, Sweden, Serbia, Romania, Moldova.

-Gender equality in the group composition is a plus.

-Eligible applicants should fill in the application form at EU Survey (<https://becultour.eu/hackathon/form>) which includes:

Team composition and a concept note describing the innovative solution. Applicants should also attach the consent form and expression of commitment (See ANNEX 2) of each teammate, which are vital for the smooth running of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme. The attachment can be uploaded directly with the application form.

2.2.2 INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS

Definition

An innovative circular tourism solution is composed of a set of product(s) and/or service(s) aimed at creating a unique experience/tourist service.

Level of maturity

The proposed innovative solution is expected to be at an idea/concept level.

Innovation areas

The innovation areas addressed by this call are: Rural Co-living, Sensorial Heritage Experience, Contemporary Meanings of Heritage, Spiritual Travel experience, Nature As Heritage, Industrial Heritage Experience, Transformative travel, Remote Working Destination, Proximity Travel, Post-cultural tourism. The innovative solution must be fully aligned with the definition of circular cultural tourism provided in section 1.1. Therefore, it should encompass Circular economy in tourism, Human-centred design & development and Cultural tourism as driver of Europeanisation. Moreover, digitalisation and smart data management features will be considered a plus.

Location

⁴ The flight and accommodation will be covered for 4 teammates according to the conditions specified in this Call.

The applicants must select one of Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites as their main area for the development of the innovative solution proposed.

3. LOCAL PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOPS

Seen that the innovative circular cultural tourism solutions will be linked with Be.CULTOUR local Action Plans for circular cultural tourism co-designed by the local community in each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site, the applicants are welcome to participate in local workshops organised by project partners in each Pilot Heritage Site. During these workshops, the applicants will have the opportunity to meet the local community, discuss and understand the local challenges. To register, please check the specific call related to each Pilot Heritage Site available in Be.CULTOUR website at <https://becultour.eu/Hackathon/PilotHeritageSites>

4. SELECTION PROCESS

The selection process will be conducted in two steps, the “Pitch session” and the “Hackathon”, as described below.

4.1 STEP 1 - PITCH SESSION

The best innovative solutions will be selected, and the teammates will be invited to pitch their innovative solution during a pitch event to be held between 23-31 May 2022. Place and time will be communicated by email.

4.1 STEP 2 - HACKATHON

What is a Hackathon

A hackathon is a design sprint event that brings together professionals from different walks of life. It spans from multiple hours to a few days during which multidisciplinary teams brainstorm and solve a challenge, create a product prototype or conduct a case study. Hackathons provide a unique opportunity for teams to collaborate intensively on the development of their ideas into desirable, feasible and viable projects and it is known to be the shortest route to innovation.

Who will participate Be.CULTOUR Hackathon?

The selected innovative circular cultural tourism solutions submitted to this open call from each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site will be invited to a 3-day hackathon in Brussels. The selected applicants are expected to commit to travel to Brussels and participate actively in the 3-day Be.CULTOUR Hackathon which will give them later on access to the Be.CULTOUR acceleration programme and the opportunity to develop and test their innovative solutions.

Be.CULTOUR Hackathon will take place from 7 to 9 September 2022, from: 09:00-18:00 at ICHEC Brussels Management School: Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6, 1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Belgium. It is planned to take place in person in English. However, given the current uncertainties regarding the course of the pandemic, ICHEC has an operational Plan B which provides for a fully virtual hackathon. In the event of force majeure, ICHEC's seasoned practitioners in distance learning processes and workshops will make sure to provide a vibrant and engaging digital experience.

Number of innovative solutions to be selected from this Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site: 3

Number of solutions participating in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon: 19

Number of participants per innovative circular cultural tourism solution: 4 people

Total number of participants: 100 participants

Outcome: a Minimum Viable Prototype⁵

⁵ For the scope of this Open Call, a Minimum Viable Prototype is a first non-marketable version of the product / service including its business model and a riskiest assumptions testing plan the team needs to dig deep into and solve in order to develop a viable go-to-market product. This MVP will drive the product/service roadmap for what the team should pilot first and what needs to be built year over year to achieve the vision.

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Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020 – Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

What are we going to do during Be.CULTOUR Hackathon?

Be.CULTOUR Hackathon is structured in three intensive days from 09:00 to 18:00. During these 3 days, participating teams will go through the following stages:

Understanding my heritage site and circular cultural tourism

Identify my ecosystem, analyze the environmental and social impacts throughout the value chain, understand the scientific and technical aspects with a focus on energy, material flows, & understand the social issues.

Building desirable, feasible, viable and resilient circular cultural tourism solutions

Operate in Design Thinking, Lean Startup, Agile mode, discover and apply the suitable Sustainable Business Model, test the designed solution, its technical feasibility, monetization and impact measurement.

Deploying the solution

Think about organizational design and governance needed to run the solution and set up a first roadmap describing next levels.

These sessions are designed as highly participatory processes that allows to move from idea generation to first solution prototyping. Business Model canvases adapted to cultural heritage sustainable tourism and circular economy approaches (i.e. inspired from the Flourishing Business Canvas; Strongly Sustainable Business Model; Inclusive Business Model) will help participants to consider the 4 main pillars of a business model: **desirability / feasibility / viability/ impact**.

During each of the above-mentioned days, a time for reflection is planned and coaching is provided by ICHEC Brussels Management school.

Be.CULTOUR Hackathon timeline

Call for proposals
2 March 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627
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Why participate in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon?

During Be.CULTOUR Hackathon, you will have the possibility to interact and work with 100 innovators from: Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites⁶; Be.CULTOUR Mirror Innovation Ecosystems⁷; and experts from European countries.

During the Hackathon the most innovative circular cultural tourism solution will be voted by a people's jury.

5. AWARD

The best solutions selected for each Pilot Heritage Site will enter the Be.CULTOUR Acceleration programme offered by ICHEC. The acceleration period will have a duration of 4 months and will be carried out on-line (except for the last meeting which will take place in person in the Pilot Heritage Site).

The acceleration period aims at making innovative circular cultural tourism solutions become concrete business solutions.

What is an acceleration period?

An acceleration period is a fixed term education, training and mentorship program accessible through a competitive application process aimed at speeding up the growth of new businesses.

What are we going to do during Be.CULTOUR acceleration period?

The 19 teams who completed successfully Be.CULTOUR Hackathon will have free access to a four-months acceleration period. A mentoring program run by ICHEC Brussels Management school which encompasses four key periods divided into tasks of 4 weeks.

Each key period starts with a meeting aiming at igniting the items to be covered during the period. The following paragraph describes the different key periods and what is expected from teams during each key period as follows:

Period I (25 October - 14 November 2022): Project structuring

A core team is identified in every Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site

Solution features are fine tuned

Solution roadmap based on a set of value streams is set up

The first iteration is planned and executed

⁶ Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Sites: Vulture-Alto Bradano in Basilicata region (Italy), the Cultural Park of the Rio Martin in Aragon region (Spain), Larnaca rural cultural landscape (Cyprus), Forsvik and Rydal industrial heritage sites in Västra Götaland region (Sweden), Bac, Irig and Sremski Karlovci historic cities in Vojvodina region (Serbia), and along the Cultural Route of Stephan the Great and Saint at the cross-border of North-East Romania and Moldova.

⁷ Be.CULTOUR Mirror Innovation Ecosystems: Nicosia Tourism Board (Cyprus), Sviluppumbria (Italy), Regione del Veneto (Italy), Savonlinna Development Services Ltd. (Finland), Municipality of Leeuwarden (The Netherlands), North-West Regional Development Agency (NWRDA) (Romania), Timis County Council (Romania), Region of Thessaly (Greece), Regional development agency Srem (Serbia), Museo Diffuso dei 5 Sensi Sciacca - Cooperativa di Comunità Identità e Bellezza (Italy), Gwynedd County Council (UK), Greater Poland Tourism Organization (Poland), University of Algarve (Portugal), Kuldiga District Municipality (Latvia), Stadsregio Parkstad Limburg (The Netherlands), Saltaire Inspired (UK).

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Period II (15 November - 12 December 2022): Assumption Testing

Riskiest Assumptions are listed and prioritized
Testing of the most critical assumptions is performed
The solution is updated according to lessons learned from the different tests

Period III (13 December 2022 - 23 January 2023): Prototyping

Pretotypes are designed (eg : landing page, storyboard)
Pretotypes are tested toward specific target customers / users
Results are analyzed and the solution is adapted accordingly

Period IV (24 January - 14 February 2023): Viability and Pitching

Financial numbers are fine tuned
Pitches are created and challenged through dry runs
Important stakeholders are identified
The project is pitched to these stakeholders in order to get a first idea about their level of readiness re an engagement in the project (eg: bringing people, money and/or any other asset)

Meeting dates:

Period I: Tuesday 25 October 2022 09:00-12:00 (VIRTUAL MEETING)
Period II: Tuesday 15 November 2022 09:00-12:00 (VIRTUAL MEETING)
Period III: Tuesday 13 December 2022 09:00-12:00 (VIRTUAL MEETING)
Period IV: Between 24 January and 14 February 2023 (face to face meeting in Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site) The exact pitch date and place will be communicated in a later stage.

During Be.CULTOUR acceleration period (25 October 2022-14 February 2023), each team has 2 wild cards of 30-minutes. This means that they can contact ICHEC's team and schedule a 30-minutes meeting to address burning questions, drawbacks, concerns, or any other matter.

Be.CULTOUR acceleration timeline

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6. WHERE AND HOW TO SEND APPLICATIONS

Application form

The application form includes: Team composition; and a concept note describing the innovative solution. Applicants should also attach the consent form and expression of commitment (See ANNEX 2) of each teammate, which are vital for the smooth running of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme. The attachment can be uploaded directly with the application form. To apply at EU Survey: <https://becultour.eu/hackathon/form>

Deadline for submission

The deadline for submission of the application is 19 of May of 2022 at 18:00 (CET)
Any application submitted after the deadline will be rejected.

7. EVALUATION AND SELECTION OF APPLICATIONS

Applications submitted to this open call will be examined and evaluated by an evaluation committee. The best applications from each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site will be invited to pitch their solution to a local jury (see §4.1 Step 1 – Pitch session) which will take place online/hybrid between 23-31 May 2022. Each group will have the opportunity to present its solution and discuss its feasibility and viability. Out of the nine pitches, three innovative circular tourism solutions will be selected from each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site.

Evaluation criteria

Innovativeness of the proposed solution 60

- Relevance to circular cultural tourism framework 30

(Circular economy aspects; Human-centred, fair and responsible tourism aspects; Cultural Europeanisation aspects)

- Relevance to the selected heritage site 20

(Contribution to the valorisation, reuse and regeneration of the target heritage site)

- Relevance to the innovation area(s) 10

(Coherence with the topics expressed in the target innovation areas, including cross-cutting areas such as digitalisation)

Expected impacts 30

(Social impact and social innovation, including benefit for local communities, engagement and/or wellbeing of cultural minorities and vulnerable social groups; Environmental impacts such as reduction of pollution, materials extraction; enhancement of biodiversity, energy, water, renewables & recycled materials use, etc.; Economic impacts in the region/site such as jobs generation potential, enhancement of local economy, increase in tourists' arrivals, etc.)

Group composition 10

(Internal skills and competences required for the implementation of the innovative solution proposed, motivation and commitment)

Should the examination of the application reveal that a submitted solution does not meet the eligibility criteria stated in Sections §2.2.1 & §2.2.2., the application will be rejected on this sole basis.

8. FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS

Call for proposals

11

2 March 2022

The best solutions/teams awarded will have the possibility to apply for further support from Be.CULTOUR project for an amount up to 96,000 € in total for all Pilot Heritage Sites to develop their Minimum Viable Product and test it in real context. The terms of reference for the applications will be specified after the Hackathon according to principles of transparency, competition and best value for money in compliance with the rules of each country.

9. ACCEPTANCE OF TERMS AND CONDITIONS

In order to respect the different innovative solutions participating in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, the selected applicants agree to attend Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme on the assigned days.

Organizers reserve the right, unilaterally and without prior notice, to exclude any applicant to the Be.CULTOUR Hackathon, if it has suspicions or detects attempts to defraud, alter and/or disable, directly or indirectly, the smooth running and ordinary, proper course of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon.

Both the initial selection committee and the Jury appointed for the different phases of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon will have the ability to interpret and complete the Terms and Conditions of this Open Call and their decisions will be final.

Non-acceptance by the applicant of any of the terms and conditions of this Open Call will also involve her/his loss of the right to participate in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme and/or obtain any prize that could be awarded.

Participation in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme involves acceptance of the whole contents of these Terms and Conditions.

The applicant states and warrants that s/he is the owner, or obtained the appropriate consent to use, all of the data and information submitted to Organizers and that such data and information do not violate the rights of third parties, as well as it is true, correct and accurate to the best of her/his knowledge.

10. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

All applicants taking part in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme declare that: they have appropriate ownership or obtained the appropriate consent to use, of the applicable intellectual property rights (trademarks, copyrights, patents etc.) on the programs, ideas, software and / or content included in their innovative solutions;

they do not infringe third parties' intellectual property rights or any other applicable national or international right with reference to the contents, ideas, software etc. The participant will defend and hold harmless the Organizers from any liability regarding the use of the above-mentioned programs, ideas and / or content, etc.

Specifically, and in relation to the content and images that the applicants may show or disclose during Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, they guarantee and are liable to Organizers and third parties for the following aspects:

They are legitimate owners or holders of rights, granting Organizers the license for their publication and, where appropriate, have obtained the necessary consent from third parties to do so.

They do not violate applicable laws such as those relating to data privacy rights, intellectual, industrial or similar property rights, honourability rights or any other right of a third party, notwithstanding if the third party is a natural person or an entity.

In the unlikely event that they publish personal details about another person during the course of the Open Call, Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, they should have previously obtained their consent for the publication.

The applicants will therefore be liable to Organizers for the accuracy of the details reported, ensuring that they do actually pertain to them and not to a third party, holding Organizers harmless from any demand or claim that, if applicable, could be made by third parties in relation to the above statements,

and any legitimate right to the content that is published and / or provided to Organizers as part of Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme.

The applicants are in any event solely liable for the consequences of damages or actions arising from use of the content and/or programs included in their innovative solutions, as well as their reproduction and diffusion.

Intellectual and/or industrial property rights for innovative solutions submitted in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme will - where appropriate in each case - belong exclusively to applicants who submitted them.

11. CONFIDENTIALITY

Throughout Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, confidentiality will be ensured with respect to the innovative solutions submitted by the applicants; Organizers only being able to diffuse, at any time and through any means, the general characteristics of these, as well as the names of these innovative solutions and those of applicants and, especially, the winners.

12. ADVERTISING BY FINALISTS AND WINNERS

When promoting the participation to Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme and its results, finalists and winners in any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) must:

- a) display the EU emblem and Be.CULTOUR logo, and
- b) include the following text:

“This innovative solution was finalist for/winner of Be.CULTOUR Open Call funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

13. PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION POLICY

Organizers inform applicants to Be.CULTOUR Open Call that it respects current legislation regarding the protection of personal data, pursuant to the provisions of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR – EU Reg. 679/16), approving the regulations implementing it, and users can at any time exercise their rights of access, rectification, cancellation and opposition regarding their personal data, communicating via email to ruba.saleh@ichec.be. In these communications, please specify the name of the applicant - your email address and, if applicable, the name of the company on behalf of which you completed the forms on the website.

The legal basis of the processing is the consent for the processing applicants' personal data for the participation in Be.CULTOUR Open Call. Without that personal data processing the application cannot be fulfilled. The applicants authorize the responsible parties and potential assignees, to send to them any information content (newsletter) expressing their consent through the applicable forms. The possible refusal will not impact the participation in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme.

A dedicated privacy policy is provided and must be read and accepted by the applicants before any application.

ICHEC undertakes to respect the confidentiality of the data included in the application and to use it in accordance with the collection purposes i.e.: to manage data regarding contact details and participants in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, to perform content delivery management (newsletters); and other purpose that might be indicated at the time of data collection. ICHEC will comply with its obligation to store data and to adopt all the reasonable measures to prevent alteration,

loss, treatment or unauthorized access in accordance with the provisions of General Data Protection Regulation.

Personal data provided by applicants must always be truthful and complete. If they are false, Organizers reserve the possibility of refusing the right to compete for the prize at any time.

Applicants to Be.CULTOUR open call know and expressly accept that in order to manage and enable their participation and to manage Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme, Organizers may use both their image and personal contact data and, in particular, their email address in order to communicate with the semi-finalists and the winners and to inform them about the steps to take to ensure their pitch presentations between 23-31 May 2022; during Be.CULTOUR Hackathon and acceleration programme and; to be awarded the prize.

Finalists and winners agree that their name will be published on the Be.CULTOUR project website (<https://www.becultour.eu/>) as part of the management for their participation. Please download and read carefully the privacy policy: <https://becultour.eu/Hackathon/privacypolicy>

14. PUBLICITY

The Be.CULTOUR Consortium may use, for its communication and publicising activities, information relating to the action, documents and any other material (such as pictures or audio-visual material) that it receives from the applicants (including in electronic form).

The Be.CULTOUR Consortium will publish on the project website and social media the name of the finalist(s) and the winner(s), their origin, the prize and its nature and purpose, unless they have requested and justified the waiver of this publication because disclosure risks threatening their security and safety or harming their commercial interest.

Photos and videos taken by Be.CULTOUR team either in preparation of the award ceremony or during the award ceremony or during any other related event organised by BE.CULTOUR Consortium are the sole property of the BE.CULTOUR Consortium.

The BE.CULTOUR Consortium will publish on the project website and social media the name of the finalists and the winners.

15. MODIFICATIONS AND CANCELLATIONS

The Organizer cannot be held liable in any way for the conduct of the participants and/or the awarding of prizes. In any case, the applicant undertakes to hold the Organizers harmless and indemnified from any and all prejudicial consequences, costs, damages - including sanctions by the competent authorities - that may arise or may arise against them as a result of its actions or violation of the Regulation. If, for whatever reason, the initiative could not be carried out in accordance with the regulations, the Organizer reserves the right, at its complete discretion, to modify or cancel the initiative, without any liability for the Organizer, undertaking to publish these modifications through the website <https://www.becultour.eu/>. Participation in the initiative is free of charge.

Furthermore, if participants wish to make any modifications or cancellations related to the information provided, they must do so by sending an email to: ruba.saleh@ichec.be.

16. LAW AND JURISDICTION

These Terms and Conditions are governed by Belgian law and the applicants and the Organizers, expressly waiving any other jurisdiction, are subject to the Court of Brussels, Belgium, for any dispute arising between the parties. The language before the court will be French.

ANNEX 1

BOX 1: What is contemporary meanings of heritage?

Contemporary interpretation of cultural heritage sites through artistic creation, linking past and future perspectives and re-generating heritage “intrinsic value”, its meanings and sense, while generating intense emotional experience addressing citizens and visitors at the same time; also, developing new forms of heritage enjoyment such as gamification and virtual travel experience, creative and unconventional story-telling for example co-developed involving residents, and augmented ways to enjoy cultural heritage such as augmented reality and immersive hybrid digital-physical experience. A contemporary interpretation of cultural heritage sites which takes place by exploring present and past local heritage through various artistic forms. Abandoned and depopulated areas can be the perfect fit that certain Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) need/look for (e.g. film, photography, video projections and light installations, theatre, dance, music, etc). CCIs can make use of the heritage “intrinsic value,” its meanings and dynamics, while generating intense emotional and aesthetic experiences.

BOX 2: What is an industrial heritage experience?

Innovative ways to create an audience for industrial heritage sites as iconic architecture places and “modern cathedrals” telling the history of European flourishing manufacturing. The industrial revolutions have always generated deep cultural changes in the society, while they have been also oriented by scientific and cultural evolutions. **The types of industries and manufacturing activities in diverse European territories have profoundly influenced local culture and history**, for example coal, mining, textile industries, while they have stimulated the development of arts and design, as in the European Bauhaus, generating **iconic architectures and products**. European industrial heritage represents a unique testimony of this creativity, while the visit to **contemporary innovative craft/production places** could be enhanced as ‘real world’ cultural experiences, also stimulating entrepreneurial spirit and promoting responsible entrepreneurial culture.

BOX 3: What is remote working destination?

Home working has been one of the primary effects of the pandemic. As the situation pursued, an increasing number of workers, especially creative and cultural industry workers, have started to look for remote working destinations.

This trend allows people to experience new places and simultaneously fulfil the duties of their profession and/or work. Remote working allows people to break the routine of their lives, regenerate physically and psychologically and experience different lifestyles closer to nature or “slow living.” Moreover, for some creative professions, such an environment could offer new perspectives and inspiration.

Some authorities and organisations in charge of tourism are looking into long-term attraction of this visitor’s segment, hoping that this trend will stay beyond the long-tail of the pandemic in order to support local economies without displacing any permanent residents’ jobs.

BOX 4: What is sensorial heritage experience?

Immersive experience of places combining new ways of **enjoying and learning about intangible cultural heritage** – such as local gastronomy, wine, craft, music, language, history and traditional skills – with a more intimate and reflexive inner journey. Sensorial heritage experience includes learning and educational activities addressed to all age groups to get in contact more deeply with the local culture and traditions through their intangible heritage expressions using the five senses. Intangible heritage is often the result of a particular cultural environment, so to take part in this heritage in the place it originates is of unique value.

BOX 5: What is nature as heritage experience?

Nature can be perceived as cultural heritage by exploring the meanings and values of natural areas, their “genius loci” recognized over centuries and millennia. Natural heritage includes also, for example, the **cultural meanings attributed to view of the sky in local cultures**, often linked with mythology and traditional practices, as in astro-tourism experiences promoted by starlight reserves initiatives. Moreover, **local biodiversity**, as autochthonous flora and fauna species, and/or important geologic areas, can become **symbols of a territory and thus part of the cultural identity of local communities**. Enjoying “nature as heritage” means also developing **eco-tourism, trekking, sports, active & adventure experiential tourism solutions** in natural heritage sites. Viewing the night sky (e.g. star-gazing, astro-tourism) and/or biodiversity observation is much easier in less inhabited and/or visited corners of Europe. Areas with small population density, (limited) accessibility, or abandoned and depopulated areas often have less air, water, soil, noise and light pollution, therefore creating the right conditions for the enjoyment of natural heritage and outdoor activities.

BOX 6: What is proximity travel?

Proximity travel, also known as “staycation” is a practice that consists in travelling close-by to one’s daily environment. Citizens re-discover nearby cultural and natural sites, becoming tourists at home. What motivates travellers to pick this option, is the willingness to rediscovering a place in a different way, organising various tourist activities, living unusual experiences and responding to a need for a break from everyday life while remaining in an environment close to home.

BOX 7: What is spiritual travel experience?

Spirituality requires introspection and reflection. For most people, these can be achieved more easily when there are limited or no distractions. When the environment is slowing down, is relaxing the mind and body, and is inspiring people to think at what matters most in life not just on ephemeral actions.

Religious heritage appreciation intertwined with nature enjoyment, joining physical and spiritual health enhancement. This includes pilgrimage routes, spiritual retreats, and other diverse ways to regenerate and conserve religious heritage places, promoting the value of religious heritage by raising public interest and encouraging community engagement in the conservation and safeguarding of Europe’s religious heritage.

BOX 8: What is rural co-living experience?

Innovative ways to promote authentic rural experiences in traditional cultural landscapes through homestay and hospitality in rural villages, stimulating relationships between citizens and visitors through their participation in traditional activities such as agricultural and landscape maintenance, as well as local arts & crafts. Such offers represent a modality to break the routine and to experience another way of living.

BOX 9: What is post-cultural tourism?

This trend refers to people seeking to explore different forms of alternative travel which aim to discover authentic 'unusual', "un-exceptional", ordinary / 'daily life' places, which are not included in conventional cultural tourism itineraries, but can be representative of the authentic, 'real' cultural life of places, also discovering particular places in which social and cultural innovation is developed by active local organizations, artists and innovators, turning visitors into 'temporary residents' (e.g. urban peripheries, industrial areas, "daily life" neighbourhoods). This includes also providing new ways to integrate visitors and residents' daily life, promoting for example locals guides and/or unconventional digital guides able to enlighten 'ordinary' places through alternative itineraries, creative interpretation and unusual / engaging storytelling.

BOX 10: What is transformative travel experience?

Transformation is stimulated by learning and educational experiences, self-reflection, self-discovery or re-discovery, and integrates the experiences enjoyed during the trip into the visitor's daily life back home. Transformative travel permanently affects us. Traveling alone can be a way to develop confidence and new social skills. This is a growing tourism segment, including not only single millennials but even middle-aged people. However, some people traveling alone or in small groups do not always feel safe and trustful of local people. This includes finding new ways for making travellers feel comfortable, find trustful local people, and develop soft skills through cultural tourism.

BOX 11: What is circular tourism?

Circular economy in the tourism sector is mainly linked to the reduction of the negative environmental externalities of the tourism industry, such as pollution and generation of waste, but it goes beyond this by embracing the wider notion of sustainability. Circular economy models in the tourism sector are related to the effort for reducing wastes and natural resources consumption (energy, water, soil, biodiversity), enhancement of green transport means, recycling and reuse of materials and products, as well as the promotion of locally based food and craft products. Moreover, circular models are related to the reduction of tourism pressure on over-exploited territories, overcoming mass tourism, seasonality and "stop-and-go" tourism, promoting less-known and less-crowded destinations, but also overcoming tourism dependency by diversifying the local economy avoiding focusing on only one economic sector or tourism typology. Associated words: circular tourism, circular city, green tourism, sustainable tourism, circular business models.

BOX 12: What is human-centred, fair and responsible tourism?

Human-centred services and products are generally linked to placing 'real' needs of people and communities at the centre of the design process, overcoming extreme standardisation and providing diverse, tailor-made experiences, considering the special needs of the person. This concept can be effectively applied to develop inclusive tourism services and products. For example, the concept of cultural tourism "for all" is based on inclusive products and services addressing people with special needs. Human-centred tourism is also based on enhancement of human capital including skills and the entrepreneurial capacity, empowering local communities to take advantage of the benefit of a sustainable tourism and enhancing local entrepreneurial innovation ecosystems through cultural tourism. From the point of view of tourism service providers, human-centred businesses are committed to respect human rights paying attention to tourism workers' rights and avoiding any exploitative measure of people in tourism-related activities. Finally, from the point of view of the visitor, the human-centred tourism is linked to fair and responsible tourism behaviour, paying attention to contribute to places sustainable development and avoiding exploitative behaviours, as it is emerging through voluntourism or 'FairBnb' experiences.

BOX 13: What is cultural Europeanisation?

The travel experience in Europe can be an opportunity to explore the extremely rich and diverse European culture, history and identity, promoting educational and recreational activities focusing on European identity, culture, history and values, as well as the development of European Cultural Routes and European Heritage Labels. Cultural Europeanisation focuses on a shared sense of belonging based on the common history and cultures expressed in European tangible and intangible cultural heritage and landscapes.

BOX 14: What is smart destination management?

ICT, AI, 5G and IoT systems can be used for better tourism flow management to avoid overcrowding, enhance accessibility and safety, and foster evidence-based policies to enhance local communities' wellbeing, as well as the visitor experience. This includes the development of applications for enhanced travel experience, for example to visit less-known and less-crowded places, discovering 'hidden treasures' or accessing creative and unconventional guides to places. Through digital tools, visitors and residents can be also facilitated to become active actors of local sustainable development policies, expressing their preferences and needs and thus participating to enhancing local context, going beyond tourism by embracing regional/local sustainable development.

A Be.CULTOUR glossary is available here: <https://www.becultour.eu/glossary/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020 – Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

ANNEX 2

Informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data

The Be.CULTOUR project ensures protection of your personal data and respect of your privacy. When carrying out this open call we adhere to the [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR) on the processing of personal data.

For more details concerning the processing of personal data within Be.CULTOUR project related to the participation of in the Hackathon, please read carefully the Privacy Policy at this link [\[https://becultour.eu/Hackathon/privacypolicy\]](https://becultour.eu/Hackathon/privacypolicy).

Participant 1 (group representative and contact person)

Name:
Surname:
Title of your innovative solution:
Email:
Country of residence:
Region:
Representative of a legal entity: yes/no
If yes: type and name of legal entity

Informed Consent

I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Policy.

I agree that ICHEC will process my contact details (name, surname, organisation, role, country and e-mail address) to re-contact me for the purpose of the organisation of the pitch session to be held online/hybrid in May 2022 and Be.CULTOUR Hackathon to be held in person in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

I have read and understood that the information received through this application form could be used for research purposes and for dissemination and communication purposes, without connection to personal data.

I hereby consent to receiving updates from Be.CULTOUR project newsletter

Yes
No

Expression of commitment

I, the undersigned, have read the proposal prepared by my group to be submitted for the Call for Proposals. In light of the above, I hereby commit to:

- Attending the three-day BeCultour Hackathon (7-9 September 2022) at ICHEC Brussels management School in Brussels;
- Following the acceleration period between 25 October 2022 and 14 February 2023;
- Cooperating with my group for the implementation of our innovative solution to the best of my ability.

Yes
No

Date

Signature

Call for proposals
2 March 2022

19

Participant 2

Name:

Surname:

Title of your innovative solution:

Email:

Country of residence:

Region:

Representative of a legal entity: yes/no

If yes: type and name of legal entity

Informed Consent

I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Policy.

I agree that ICHEC will process my contact details (name, surname, organisation, role, country and e-mail address) to re-contact me for the purpose of the organisation of the pitch session to be held online/hybrid in May 2022 and Be.CULTOUR Hackathon to be held in person in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

I have read and understood that the information received through this application form could be used for research purposes and for dissemination and communication purposes, without connection to personal data.

I hereby consent to receiving updates from Be.CULTOUR project newsletter

Yes

No

Expression of commitment

I, the undersigned, have read the proposal prepared by my group to be submitted for the Call for Proposals. In light of the above, I hereby commit to:

-Attending the three-day BeCultour Hackathon (7-9 September 2022) at ICHEC Brussels management School in Brussels;

-Following the acceleration period between 25 October 2022 and 14 February 2023;

-Cooperating with my group for the implementation of our innovative solution to the best of my ability.

Yes

No

Date

Signature

Participant 3

Name:

Surname:

Title of your innovative solution:

Email:

Country of residence:

Region:

Representative of a legal entity: yes/no

If yes: type and name of legal entity

Informed Consent

I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Policy.

I agree that ICHEC will process my contact details (name, surname, organisation, role, country and e-mail address) to re-contact me for the purpose of the organisation of the pitch session to be held online/hybrid in May 2022 and Be.CULTOUR Hackathon to be held in person in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

I have read and understood that the information received through this application form could be used for research purposes and for dissemination and communication purposes, without connection to personal data.

I hereby consent to receiving updates from Be.CULTOUR project newsletter

Yes

No

Expression of commitment

I, the undersigned, have read the proposal prepared by my group to be submitted for the Call for Proposals. In light of the above, I hereby commit to:

- Attending the three-day BeCultour Hackathon (7-9 September 2022) at ICHEC Brussels management School in Brussels;
- Following the acceleration period between 25 October 2022 and 14 February 2023;
- Cooperating with my group for the implementation of our innovative solution to the best of my ability.

Yes

No

Date

Signature

Participant 4
Name:
Surname:
Title of your innovative solution:
Email:
Country of residence:
Region:
Representative of a legal entity: yes/no
If yes: type and name of legal entity

Informed consent
I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Policy.

I agree that ICHEC will process my contact details (name, surname, organisation, role, country and e-mail address) to re-contact me for the purpose of the organisation of the pitch session to be held online/hybrid in May 2022 and Be.CULTOUR Hackathon to be held in person in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

I have read and understood that the information received through this application form could be used for research purposes and for dissemination and communication purposes, without connection to personal data.

I hereby consent to receiving updates from Be.CULTOUR project newsletter
Yes
No

Expression of commitment
I, the undersigned, have read the proposal prepared by my group to be submitted for the Call for Proposals. In light of the above, I hereby commit to:
-Attending the three-day BeCultour Hackathon (7-9 September 2022) at ICHEC Brussels management School in Brussels;
-Following the acceleration period between 25 October 2022 and 14 February 2023;
-Cooperating with my group for the implementation of our innovative solution to the best of my ability.

Yes
No

Date Signature

Annex 2 – APPLICATION FORM ON EU SURVEY

Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals

Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions
Hackathon and acceleration opportunity

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627
Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020
– Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals

Under the frame of the Horizon 2020 funded project 'Beyond Cultural Tourism (Be.CULTOUR)', ICHEC Brussels Management School is opening a call for passionate innovators to shaping the future of cultural tourism in six European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova.

19 applications will be selected to participate in Be.CULTOUR Hackathon which will take place in Brussels from 7 to 9 September 2022.

Selected applicants will be given the opportunity to access Be.CULTOUR Accelerator, a training programme of 4 months in which they will have the possibility to develop their innovative solutions to a close-to-market stage.

Starting from the challenges linked to the targeted deprived, remote or over-exploited areas, the selected participants will develop circular cultural tourism services and/or products that will focus on creating attractive destinations taking into account post COVID-19 pandemic scenarios.

The Objective of the Open Call is to select the best innovative solutions to the challenges of each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site.

Please select your Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site:

at most 1 choice(s)

- Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy
- The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain
- Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus
- Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden
- Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
- The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

Please select your innovation area(s):

at most 10 choice(s)

- Rural Co-living
- Sensorial Heritage Experience
- Contemporary Meanings of Heritage
- Spiritual Travel experience
- Nature As Heritage
- Industrial Heritage Experience
- Transformative travel
- Remote Working Destination
- Proximity Travel
- Post-cultural tourism

Team composition

PRESENT YOUR TEAM (4 people)

Participant 1

Gender:

Professional background:
Role in the solution development:

60 character(s) maximum

Participant 2

Gender:
Professional background:
Role in the solution development:

60 character(s) maximum

Participant 3

Gender:
Professional background:
Role in the solution development:

60 character(s) maximum

Participant 4

Gender:
Professional background:
Role in the solution development:

60 character(s) maximum

Concept note

INNOVATIVE CIRCULAR TOURISM SOLUTION TITLE

30 character(s) maximum

INNOVATIVE CIRCULAR TOURISM SOLUTION OVERALL DESCRIPTION

2000 character(s) maximum

RELEVANCE OF THE SOLUTION FOR THE PILOT HERITAGE SITE

Describe the relevance of your solution to the selected site: Contribution to the valorization, reuse and regeneration of the Pilot Heritage Site.

2000 character(s) maximum

INNOVATIVE CIRCULAR TOURISM SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The description should illustrate how the three main concepts of Be.CULTOUR framework and definition of circular cultural tourism are incorporated in your solution: Circular economy aspects; Human-centred, fair and responsible tourism aspects; Cultural Europeanisation aspects.

2000 character(s) maximum

INNOVATION AREA(S)

Specify which of the areas of innovation your proposal refers to and specify which elements make it innovative? Describe the coherence with the topics expressed in the target innovation areas, including cross-cutting areas such as digitalisation and smart data management if relevant.

2000 character(s) maximum

IMPACTS DIMENSIONS OF YOUR SOLUTION

What are the economic, social and environmental impacts of your solution? Consider the following aspects, if relevant:

Social impact and social innovation, including benefit for local communities, engagement and/or wellbeing of cultural minorities and vulnerable social groups; Environmental impacts such as reduction of pollution, materials extraction, enhancement of biodiversity, energy, water, renewables & recycled materials use, etc.; Economic impacts in the region/site such as jobs generation potential, enhancement of local economy, increase in tourists' arrivals, etc.)

2000 character(s) maximum

TO WHICH SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL(S) DOES THIS SOLUTION DIRECTLY CONTRIBUTE ?

For more information on SDGs : <https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/sustainable-development-goals.html>

at most 17 choice(s)

- SDG1 No poverty
- SDG2 Zero hunger
- SDG3 Good health and wellbeing
- SDG4 Quality education
- SDG5 Gender equality
- SDG6 Clean water and sanitation
- SDG7 Affordable and clean energy
- SDG8 Decent work and economic growth
- SDG9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure
- SDG10 Reduce inequalities
- SDG11 Sustainable cities and communities
-

- SDG12 Responsible consumption and production
- SDG13 Climate action
- SDG14 Life below water
- SDG15 Life on land
- SDG16 Peace, justice and strong institutions
- SDG17 Partnerships for the Goals

Please add one image that summarizes your innovative circular cultural tourism solution

Please upload your image(s)

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

Informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data

The Be.CULTOUR project ensures protection of your personal data and respect of your privacy. When carrying out this open call we adhere to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR) on the processing of personal data.

For more details concerning the processing of personal data within Be.CULTOUR project related to the participation of in the Hackathon, please download and read carefully the Privacy Policy. To download it, please click here:

Download Be.CULTOUR call for proposals privacy policy

[Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals Privacy policy.pdf](#)

Applicant consent form and expression of commitment

Download Be.CULTOUR informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data

[Be.CULTOUR Informed Consent Form for the processing of personal data annex 2.pdf](#)

Participant 1 (group representative and contact person)

Name:

Surname:

Email:

Country of residence:

Region:

60 character(s) maximum

Representative of a legal entity:

- Yes
- No

If yes: type and name of legal entity

60 character(s) maximum

I am entitled to submit the concept note including personal data of all team members, who have declared to have read and understood the privacy policy and are aware of the terms for the processing of personal data:

- Yes
 No

Please upload the informed consent and expression of commitment of teammate 1

Please upload the informed consent and expression of commitment of teammate 2

Please upload the informed consent and expression of commitment of teammate 3

Please upload the informed consent and expression of commitment of teammate 4

Date

before 19/05/2022

Annex 3 – LOCAL JURY EVALUATION CRITERIA

The evaluation sheet reported the same grading announced in Be.CULTOUR open call namely:

1. Innovativeness of the proposed solution 60

1.1- Relevance to circular cultural tourism framework 30

(Circular economy aspects; Human-centred, fair and responsible tourism aspects; Cultural Europeanisation aspects)

1.2- Relevance to the selected heritage site 20

(Contribution to the valorisation, reuse and regeneration of the target heritage site)

1.3- Relevance to the innovation area(s) 10

(Coherence with the topics expressed in the target innovation areas, including cross-cutting areas such as digitalisation)

2-Expected impacts 30

(Social impact and social innovation, including benefit for local communities, engagement and/or wellbeing of cultural minorities and vulnerable social groups; Environmental impacts such as reduction of pollution, materials extraction; enhancement of biodiversity, energy, water, renewables & recycled materials use, etc.; Economic impacts in the region/site such as jobs generation potential, enhancement of local economy, increase in tourists' arrivals, etc.)

3-Group composition 10

(Internal skills and competences required for the implementation of the innovative solution proposed, motivation and commitment).

Annex 4 – HACKATHON GUIDELINES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627

H2020 Be.CULTOUR Hackathon

Participants guidelines

07-09 September 2022

ICHEC Brussels Management School
Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6
1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre
Belgium

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INTRODUCTION

Under the frame of H2020 project Be.CULTOUR, Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM – ISFSC (hereinafter abbreviated as ICHEC) launched an open call for passionate innovators eager at shaping the future of cultural tourism in six European regions: Basilicata (Italy), Aragon (Spain), Larnaca (Cyprus), Vojvodina (Serbia) and the cross-border area of North-East Romania and Moldova.

Be.CULTOUR Call for proposals was open from 02 March to 19 May 2022. Applicants submitted their concept notes via EU Survey platform and in total, 35 applications were received. Overall, six local juries, one in each Pilot Heritage Site (PHS), were set up to evaluate the concept notes. Applicants were invited to pitch their innovative solutions before a local jury. Following the local jury's deliberations, 19 innovative circular cultural tourism solutions were selected from Be.CULTOUR 6 PHS to travel to Brussels and participate in Be.CULTOUR hackathon between 07-09 September 2022 in order to move from idea generation to first solution prototyping.

Each Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site (PHS) invited between 8-13 people to act as jury members. Each jury was composed by knowledgeable professionals about the needs of their PHS representing a multiplicity of stakeholders including public & private sectors, civil society organizations and minorities. Gender equality was also taken into consideration. Each team had the opportunity to pitch for 10 minutes before its jury. Each jury member used a grading out of 100 points based on the evaluation criteria which was published in the open call (<https://becultour.eu/hackathon>).

In total, 35 applications were received and 19 solutions were selected to participated in Be.CULTOUR hackathon and Be.CULTOUR Acceleration programme.

List of the 19 selected solutions:

Pilot Heritage Site : Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy
Cammino Lucano; Fly On Tour Immersivo; Triple L tourism Leave, Learn, Live.

Pilot Heritage Site: The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain
Aridscape the wide as heritage; Eco glamping; La chica cabeza de bosque.

Pilot Heritage Site: Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus
Kalosorisete; Needle Festivals; Sensory Bee Nature Trail.

Pilot Heritage Site: Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden
Create, Design & Engage; Forsviks Chaice; Prova-Bo long-term rentals.

Pilot Heritage Site: Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
Bač By Touch; Cultural overload - Irig road; Frušking 8x4x4.

Pilot Heritage Site: The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
E-cool tour; Stephan route update, Digital Nomads Platform DNP; The Bison Land's Heritage.

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PROGRAMME

Day 1, Wednesday 07 September 2022

ICHEC Brussels Management School: Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6, 1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Belgium.

Time	Activity	Room
08:00-09:00	Registration	Espace Roger demain
09:00-09:30	Welcome remarks and introduction to Be.CULTOUR hackathon methodology	Auditorium
09:40-10:40	Understand / Macro-level - Cause and Consequence Tree	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
10:40-10:55	Coffee break	Cafeteria
10:55-12:15	Understand / Macro-level - Value chain & stakeholders mapping	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
12:15-13:05	Lunch	Cafeteria
13:05-13:20	Energizer	Espace Roger Demain or terrace
13:20-13:35	Understand / Micro-level - Introduction to the Empathy phase	Auditorium
13:35-14:15	Understand / Micro-level - User / Client segments defined	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
14:15-16:30	Understand / Micro-level - Collection of needs	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
16:30-16:45	Coffee break	Cafeteria
16:45-17:45	Define - Define the "real" problems of the challenge	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
17:45-18:00	Retrospective - Learning as a team	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

ICHEC coaches can also use room 411

Be.CULTOUR consortium partners are welcome to use room 421

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Day 2, Thursday 08 September 2022

ICHEC Brussels Management School: Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6, 1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Belgium.

Time	Activity	Room
08:45-09:05	Ideate - Introduction to Step 3 (Ideate) and to the Societal Impact Canvas	Auditorium
09:05-09:50	Ideate - Inspiration - consultation of positive impact maps and examples	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
09:50-10:50	Ideate - Solution design - Diverging phase	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
10:50-11:05	Coffee break	Cafeteria
11:05-11:25	Ideate - Solution design - Converging phase	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
11:25-12:10	Ideate - Solution design - Description with the help of the Societal Impact Canvas	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
12:10-12:55	Lunch	Cafeteria
12:55-13:15	Prototype - Overview of Stages 4 (Prototype), 5 (Test) and 6 (Monetization) Introduction to the construction of a Value Proposition, the RAT and the Storyboard	Auditorium
13:15-14:30	Prototype - First Minimal Testable Solution (MTS)	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
14:30-16:45	Test - Test MTS	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
16:45-17:00	Coffee break	Cafeteria
17:00-17:30	Test - Update MTS	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region

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		222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
17:30-18:00	Test - Cross-team Feedback session - Dry test	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

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Optional activity at La Vallée: Rue Adolphe Lavallée 39, 1080 Bruxelles

<https://lavallee.brussels/>

Time	Activity	Remark
19:00-20:00	Visit to La Vallée	A maximum of 50 people can join the visit. The list of participants will be assigned on a first register-first-serve basis.
20:00-22:00	Casual dinner at La Vallée	Food truck with meat and vegan hamburgers. Drink tokens will be provided.

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Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

Day 3, Friday 09 September 2022

ICHEC Brussels Management School: Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6, 1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Belgium.

Time	Activity	Room
09:00-09:20	Introduction to the program for the day	Auditorium
09:20-10:40	Prototype - Viability of the solution	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
10:40-11:10	Prototype - Feasibility of the solution	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
11:10-11:25	Coffee break	Cafeteria
11:25-12:40	Prototype & Test Business model visualisation Impact wheel Last prototype tests	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
12:40-13:25	Lunch	Cafeteria
13:25-14:00	Pitch fine-tuning	201: Basilicata Region 211: Aragon region 221: Larnaca Region 222: Västra Götaland Region 231: Vojvodina Region 232: North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
14:10-15:40	Pitching before the jury	211: Jury 1 221: Jury 2 222: Jury 3 231: Jury 4 232: Jury 5
15:40-15:55	Jury deliberation / Coffee break for participants	Jury room Cafeteria
16:00-16:40	Visualisation of the 19 videos Results of the popular vote on-line	Auditorium Streaming : YouTube ICHEC
16:40-17:00	Announcement of the best 5 innovative solutions Concluding remarks	Auditorium Streaming : YouTube ICHEC
17:00-18:30	Cocktail	Duc 2

ICHEC coaches can also use room 411

Be.CULTOUR consortium partners are welcome to use room 421

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IMPORTANT NOTES FOR PARTICIPANTS

- **Location:** ICHEC Brussels Management School: Boulevard Brand Whitlock 6, 1150 Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Belgium.
- **Timetable:** Day 1, Wednesday 07 September 2022, 09:00-18:00. Day 2, Thursday 08 September 2022, 08:45-18:00. Day 3, Friday 09 September 2022, 09:00-17:00.
- **Hackathon registration:** To confirm your participation and dietary needs. Please register here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/d86ab804-619f-cbdf-5399-5b721f148883>
Please register by 21 August 2022 at 23:00 (11 PM) at the latest.
- **Registration desk at ICHEC:** Please come by the registration desk at Espace Roger demain on Wednesday 07 September 2022 between 08:00 and 09:00 to pick up your Be.CULTOUR hackathon materials.
- **Coffee breaks and lunch:** Food and beverage will be served at the cafeteria. Please respect the allocated timeslot. Vegetables are local and most of them come from a closed loop.

Optional visit: On Thursday 08 September 2022, an optional visit to La Vallée is foreseen. In case of interest, please register. A maximum of 50 people can join the visit. The list of participants will be assigned on a first register-first-serve basis. Address: Rue Adolphe Lavallée 39, 1080 Bruxelles. Website: <https://lavallee.brussels/>
- **Networking dinner at La Vallée:** On Thursday 08 September 2022, an optional light casual dinner is foreseen. Dinner will be provided by a Food truck offering meat and vegan hamburgers. Drink tokens will be provided as well.
- **Cocktail:** on Friday 09 September 2022 at 17:00, the cocktail will take place at Duc2. Please follow your coach.
- **Equipment's:** We encourage you to bring your own laptop. In any case, two laptops per group would suffice. Each team will have its Miro board. The same Miro board will be used during the acceleration programme. Please bring also a USB stick to save your final pitch on it. Kindly email your final pitch to your coach as well on Friday 09 September 2022 at 13:50 at the latest. Your coach will provide you with her/his email on Day 1.
- **Video:** On Friday 09 September 2022 between 09:40-11:45 we will shoot a standard 1-minute video for the 19 solutions. Don't forget that your video must be understandable by anyone and not more than 60 seconds!
Your 1-minute video specifications:
Each team should send 1 or 2 teammates max. 2 because it could be nice in multi-gender teams to have a diversity in the presentation of the video. Each team should address the following three questions:
What is your innovative solution about? What's your secret sauce that makes the difference?
What positive impacts / transformations does it bring to your Pilot Heritage Site?
What is your motto?
Keep in mind that 1-minute video is maximum 150 words. Please agree on your text before the shooting session. Every team will have 5 minutes to record its 1-minute video as follows:

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Room 621 (follow your coach)

09:40-10:00

Pilot Heritage Site : Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy
Cammino Lucano; Fly On Tour Immersivo; Triple L tourism Leave, Learn, Live.

10:00-10:20

Pilot Heritage Site: The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain
Aridscape the wide as heritage; Eco glamping; La chica cabeza de bosque.

10:20-10:40

Pilot Heritage Site: Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus
Kalosorisete; Needle Festivals; Sensory Bee Nature Trail.

10:40-11:00

Pilot Heritage Site: Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden
Create, Design & Engage; Forsviks Choice; Prova-Bo long-term rentals.

11:00-11:20

Pilot Heritage Site: Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
Bač By Touch; Cultural overload - Irig road; Frušking 8x4x4.

11:20-11:45

Pilot Heritage Site: The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area
E-cool tour; Stephan route update, Digital Nomads Platform DNP; The Bison Land's Heritage.

- **Waste:** Be.CULTOUR hackathon is waste free. Soft drinks and water will be available in glass bottles (no plastic). Glasses, plates and cutlery will be biodegradable. Lunch might be served with washable plates and cutlery.

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Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

FARES

- STIB 1 journey : 2,10€ (contactless payment) / 2,60€ (paper ticket)
- STIB 1 day : 7,50€ (contactless payment) / 8€ (paper ticket)
- Brupass 1 journey : 2,40€ (bought outside of the vehicle) (+ MOBIB basic = 5€)
- Brupass 10 journeys : 15,60€ (+ MOBIB basic = 5€)
- Brupass 1 day : 7,80€ (+ MOBIB basic = 5€)
- Go2City 1 journey - bus 12 from Brussels Airport: 7 € (contactless payment) / 7,50 € (bought outside of the vehicle)
- 1 journey STIB + SNCB : 4,20€

CYCLING

If you are passionate about cycling, you can rent a bike here:

www.villo.be

www.provelo.org

<https://billy.bike>

TAXI

-The price per km (1,8 € or 2,70 € depending on whether the journey is inside or outside the 19 districts of Brussels);

-Fixed charge: 2,40 € (4,40 € at night) ;

-The waiting time: 30,00 € per hour; certain companies charge reduced fares for journeys to the airport.

Autolux : Tel. +32 (0)2 411 41 42

Taxis Bleus : Tel. +32 (0)2 268 00 00

Taxi Victor Cab : Tel. +32 (0)2 425 25 25

Taxis Verts : Tel. +32 (0)2 349 49 49

ACCOMMODATION

Please liaise with your Pilot Heritage Site coordinator

GOING AROUND

Food and beverage

<https://visit.brussels/en/category/restaurants>

cultural agenda

<https://agenda.brussels/en/>

Brussels Museums

<https://www.brussel museums.be/en/>

Art in Brussels

<https://visit.brussels/en/article/brussels-best-contemporary-art-hotspots>

Parks in Brussels

<https://visit.brussels/en/lists/parks-in-brussels>

Nightlife

<https://visit.brussels/en/category/nightclubs>

USEFUL NUMBERS

Emergency number

100 or 112 (for health and fire emergencies)

Police

101